

D2.3:

Archetypes and methodology for designing Governance & Collaborative Business Models for OFLW Data Space and Applications

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Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Table 1 Glossary of terms and acronyms used

Acronym / Term	Description
BM	Business Model
BMC	Business Model Canvas
DSC	Data Sharing Coalition
F2F	Farm-to-Fork
FLW	Food Loss and Waste
DATA SPACE	International Data Space
IDSA	International Data Space Association
SDBM/R	Service-Dominant Business Model Radar
SILL	Systemic Innovations Living Labs

Executive summary

The goal of this document is to describe a methodology for designing the (alliance) governance and collaborative business models that ensure the sustainable exploitation of OFLW applications and data space. Business model and governance decision making are key to develop new data spaces, explaining both the *value* as well as *rules for collaboration and interaction*. However, business models and governance are highly interlinked, featuring many concurrent design choices – as a consequence, developing data spaces can be highly complex. To reduce this complexity, design support in terms of methods and tools is needed.

Other initiatives are investigated to determine the best practices (in terms of validated methods, approaches to support business model and governance development) based on the most recent developments and expertise. Synthesis of literature and especially initiatives like PLOUTOS, Data Sharing Coalition and the “Rule book for a fair data economy” from SITRA has provided valuable insights for the proposed methodology and a rich set of tools.

This deliverable presents the initial version of an approach to support decision making on governance and business models in the context of data space development. This approach is intended to be used by the SILLs in ZeroW to support the development of data spaces for safe data sharing in each of the SILLs, clarifying what business decisions (in terms of business models and governance structure) should be made and when these should be made. Additionally, the approach emphasizes the importance of thinking about what value propositions or business models can be enabled through the deployment and use of a novel data space, as well as stresses the importance of understanding what governance model is best applicable here.

This document describes:

- A comprehensive inventory of appropriate EU initiatives regarding business and governance models;
- *Methodology and tools* collected from best practices of other initiatives, to create business and governance models for sustainable OFLW implementations;
- *An approach* for operationalisation of the proposed methodology to include the phases for exploration, design, evaluation, quantitative detailing, planning and monitoring;
- *Recommendations* for further refinement and application within ZeroW.

Analysis of the literature has highlighted that an approach to support data space development in terms of decision making on the governance structure or business model aspects was not yet available: although stand-alone methods and tools have been developed for business modelling and research has conceptually addressed

how governance is relevant for business models, no support currently exists to integrate and operationalize both concepts. The proposed approach for setting up the business model aspects for the collaborative exchange of information along the supply chain and the governance decisions needed to do so is therefore the main research contribution of task T2.2. Although the business modelling tools can be partly re-used (but requires adaptation to accommodate the characteristics of data spaces), we have developed the approach to support governance decision making as part of this deliverable as no tool was identified to serve as a starting point. To do so, we have built upon existing governance models introduced and analysed how these models overlap and what aspects are addressed. On the basis of this, we propose an approach to iteratively deal with these concepts for governance decision making.

This document provides an easy overview of these tools (business modelling and governance decision making) but also a way of working and guidance on how to use them and to integrate both concepts for data space development. Scalability and federation of business- and IT services have been taken into account to increase the adaption of the ZeroW concepts to enable more and better collaboration along the supply chain, with the goal to reduce food waste. It is our belief that the proposed methodology for the OFLW domain can also be used within other domains.

The approach concerns an initial version: through use of the approach by the SILLs in ZeroW, the objective is to capture feedback on the usefulness and ease-of-use of the approach. Using the approach, we expect that SILLs will be able to understand the value that is created by means of a (local) data space in terms of associated business models (for example to counteract FLW or to support digital innovations aimed at efficient food production), how this data space is supported and what governance decisions are made in terms of participation, data exchange and collaboration protocols and policies. It should also provide input to SILLs on how to scale their data space over time (i.e. to connect data spaces based on shared value propositions). Using the approach, it should become apparent where the strengths and weaknesses of the approach are and how its usefulness can be improved. Based on this feedback, the proposed approach will be improved further as part of upcoming tasks within WP2 and the resulting business and governance models to be used will be included in the corresponding project deliverables.

1. Introduction

ZeroW aims at reducing Food Loss and Waste by employing systemic innovations, to halve by 2030 and to near-zero by 2050. This systemic innovation approach is based on the development of a core demonstrative environment supporting nine Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) along the value chain, complemented by assessment activities to ensure a long term environmental and economic sustainability of zero-FLW (OFLW) solutions and a just transition towards a near-zero FLW system.

Figure 1: ZeroW at glance

Figure 2: ZeroW approach

Figure 1 and Figure 2 illustrate the context for the ZeroW project, as well as the objectives to be achieved as part of ZeroW. This deliverable is part of WP2 – OFLW Data Space, for which the objective is to establish semantic interoperability through a managed European OFLW Data Space and to provide collaborative business and

governance models for data sharing, for the digital support needed by both the ZeroW SILLs and by external users / solution developers in the future, to reduce FLW.

1.1. Motivation for this deliverable

In the past decade, addressing the challenge of FLW (FLW) has received considerable attention in policy circles, academia and even private sectors (Cattaneo et al., 2021). Increasingly, we are as a society becoming aware of the prevalence of FLW in our modern society: close to one third of all food that is produced is ultimately wasted (Aramyan et al., 2021; Cattaneo et al., 2021). Logically, this has significant (negative) impact on the sustainability of food production, the efficient use of natural resources, as well as supporting or ensuring food availability to those in need. The COVID pandemic has further accentuated the need to focus on (reducing) FLW: supply chains have at least temporarily been disrupted as a result of social distances practices whereas food demand may have shifted as a result of the pandemic (Laborde et al., 2020). As a result, increases in losses of food can be expected even though access to food is not always guaranteed. It raises the importance of addressing FLW as part of wider research and policy making agendas.

Initiatives to reduce FLW are increasingly emerging: amongst others, initiatives exist in Brazil (Matzembacher et al., 2021), the Netherlands (Aramyan et al., 2021) and Japan (Yamada et al., 2017), illustrating that food loss is globally addressed. In ZeroW, the Systemic Innovation Living Labs (SILLs) represent similar environments to test the systemic innovations counteracting FLW and to contribute towards the sustainability and availability of food. Although the SILLs in principle are developed in closed environments (e.g., initiatives which are locally orchestrated), ZeroW has the goal to transfer learnings or even solutions between initiatives. This federated setup calls for compatibility between SILLs in terms of how they are supported, and should allow for scaling of the amount of SILLs based on common standards or principles that result from this need for compatibility / interconnectedness.

In parallel to the developments in terms of (research on) FLW, we see that globalization and digitization are increasingly impacting modern day business practices, but also enable new value propositions to organisations and end-users by means of more widespread and / or improved forms of communication, data sharing and interconnection. Data spaces are increasingly becoming more prevalent to enable data sharing between organisations. It represents a virtual space for data in which data remains at the owner until it is needed by trusted business partners (Otto et al., 2019). How the data is shared and how rights for this data are distributed is defined by the collective of organisations participating in the data space. Through the standardized structure of a data space, data sharing can be facilitated quickly, enabling organisations to establish new services or enhance or improve existing

value propositions. Additionally, new business partners or organisations can readily be connected to the DATA SPACE as opposed to bilateral means of communication and data exchange (which would require individual connections between organisations).

As mentioned, in ZeroW, the development and use of data spaces is investigated to reduce FLW: through data sharing between (food) supply chain stakeholders, new solutions can be enabled to counteract FLW, or transparency can be created on food availability for the supply chain to repurpose left-over or otherwise non-utilised food. Supply chain alignment through data sharing can contribute towards realizing reductions for FLW: collectively, supply chains can better match supply and demand or can better respond to surpluses of food available. Facilitating data availability, consistency, accessibility and transparency is therefore key. This is not only important for locally orchestrated initiatives, but also between initiatives, sharing data across supply chains to tackle global problems. Logically, this calls for initial compatibility in terms of how data spaces are orchestrated, and agreements and protocols on how and what data is shared. It is the goal for ZeroW to provide such support: to help federated data spaces as part of local initiatives (OFLW), that can be seen as ecosystems, to grow (as open ecosystems) and to become interconnected to support solving global problems such as FLW, as a federation of ecosystems (see Figure 3). This calls for support on the standardization of initial data spaces as well as thinking ahead how data spaces can be scaled and interconnected over time.

Figure 3: Evolution of local (closed) initiatives towards interconnected (global) initiatives (Otto, 2022)

Although the technical specification supporting the development of data spaces has already received attention, i.e., as part of D2.1 in ZeroW (Cornelisse, 2022) and formal specifications as part of Otto et al. (2022), the *business development* for data spaces has been under investigation. Although the importance is stressed to understand the business or organizational aspects of data spaces (OpenDEI, 2021) methodological support is lacking on what *business model* and *governance* decisions should be made by stakeholders to support the development of data spaces. Without such support, important aspects regarding the viability or feasibility of such data spaces may be left untouched:

- Does it make sense to pursue or scale the data space?
- Who will benefit through the use of the data space? How is value shared?
- What agreements need to be made on data that can be shared as part of the data space?
- Who is allowed to join for the data space? How are rights, roles and responsibilities distributed? Why?

Business models are important to consider as they articulate *value creation and value capture* (i.e. costs and benefits) for stakeholders involved (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010): business models can describe how the data space enables new value propositions, warranting its existence and driving business participation for the data space. Business models make explicit how the technology (data space) is used to create new or improve upon existing solutions as well as how stakeholders involved interact with the data space. They also clarify what purpose (in terms of data sharing) the data space should have and what this means for the technical infrastructure needed. Therefore, understanding and designing the business models enabled by means of the data space can help decision makers in articulating the value of new data spaces (as well as for the context in which it is applied) and generate commitment of stakeholders to participate. To stimulate cooperation and co-creation, such business models should be *collaborative* in nature: to design collaborative business models that are mutually beneficial for all stakeholders involved.

As stakeholders and business models can co-exist for the data space (and even between data spaces) and interact to exchange data and create value, it is also important to determine how interactions between stakeholders and business models are governed to drive and support value creation and capture (Provan & Kenis, 2008). *This governance structure* should be compatible or enable the data space business models to thrive. Therefore, in close connection to business models, the governance structure for the data space should be considered to support data space development, which calls for design decisions on how organizations or stakeholders collaborate, how rights are distributed between stakeholders and how data is exchanged for the data space.

Despite their importance, it is unclear how these activities (collaborative business modelling and modelling the governance structure) should be codesigned to support data space development. No approach is available that helps in clarifying what design decisions should be made during data space development and how concepts such as business models and governance structures should be jointly considered during the development and operation of data spaces.

In light of this gap, in this deliverable, we focus on proposing an approach to decision making on the governance structure and business models for the development of data spaces, positioned in the context of FLW. Such an approach can be used by the

SILLs to support decision making on the development, deployment, and use of the data space in practice and to connect data space development to challenges regarding FLW. Accordingly, our research objective is as follows:

“To design an approach to support the design of the governance and business models for the development of data spaces for growing data sharing initiatives and applications aimed at reducing FLW”.

To do so, we follow a design science research approach (Peffer et al., 2007), iteratively designing the approach building upon literature concerning data spaces, collaborative business models and governance models. Our approach consists of three layers for which design decisions should be made to support data space development: namely *application-specific business models*, *data space business models* and *data space governance*. Our approach builds upon existing tools proposed for collaborative business modelling (developed as part of the H2020 Ploutos project (Berkers et al., 2022)) to support the decision making on data space business models and application-specific business models. As currently there is not any method for designing the data space governance, we synthesize upon existing literature and available tools for governance as part of this deliverable to propose such an approach. The combined use of the tools for business modelling and governance should help stakeholders in making design decisions towards the development of data spaces.

We have evaluated the initial validity and usefulness of the approach in close collaboration with stakeholders for the SILLs as part of an interactive workshop in ZeroW. It is the intention that (stakeholders for) the SILLs use the approach to support the development of data spaces to counteract FLW. It is expected that, through use of the approach, SILLs initially focus on the development of a local data space to enable specific value propositions relevant to their context. However, the approach should facilitate that scaling of the data spaces over time will occur and incorporates this as part of the support given. Through *actual* use of the approach, the strengths, weaknesses and merits of using the approach in terms of data space development should become apparent. We can expect that additional feedback on its use and usefulness will be generated through its use, which will be used to further improve or refine the approach. Therefore, the approach presented in this deliverable represents an *initial (alpha)* artefact to be improved over time.

1.2. Mapping ZeroW outputs

Purpose of this chapter is to map ZeroW Grant Agreement commitments, both within the formal Deliverable and Task description, against the current document.

Table 2 Adherence to ZeroW Grant Agreement deliverable and work description

ZEROW GA Component Title	ZEROW GA Component Outline	Respective Document Chapter(s)	Justification
DELIVERABLE			
D2.3: Archetypes and methodology for designing Governance and Collaborative Business Models for OFLW Data Space and Applications	<i>Archetypes and methodology for designing Governance and Collaborative Business Models for OFLW Data Space and Applications</i>	<i>Chapter 2 Chapter 3 Chapter 5 Chapter 6</i>	<i>Chapter 2 details relevant tools and methods (for collaborative business models and governance) on which the methodology / approach as part of this deliverable is built. Here, we identify that in order to propose a methodology to support governance decision making, a synthesis of current governance literature is needed. This synthesis is conducted as per Chapter 3 and serves as the foundation for developing the methodology. Next, Chapter 5 integrates the identified tools as part of the methodology and 'operationalizes' its use for OFLW data space and applications. Chapter 6 serves as the 'theoretical' backbone to the methodology, highlighting what questions should be answered throughout the use of the methodology to guide data space development.</i>

TASKS			
<p>T2.2 Governance and collaborative business model approach for OFLW applications and OFLW data space</p>	<p><i>This Task will set up the methodology for designing the (alliance) governance and collaborative business models that ensure the sustainable exploitation of OFLW applications and data space. The work will include identification of appropriate governance and collaborative business model archetypes for data sharing and data driven services. Key principles for the methodology to establish in the design are sustainability through OFLW. An important characteristic is to design for scale and federation, as there will be data driven OFLW applications in ZeroW and outside in concurrent development. These must be able to 'onboard'. The methodology is to be applied in the application innovations in scope of the SILLs as well as for the dataspace and its collective provisions. The methodology will include the exploration, design, evaluation, quantitative detailing, planning and monitoring phases.</i></p>	<p><i>Chapter 2 Chapter 3 Chapter 5 Chapter 6</i></p>	<p><i>See description above. In addition to this, our methodology includes phases related to exploration, piloting (design, evaluation, quantitative detailing) operation (planning and monitoring) and scaling; we take into account that the OFLW Data Space is scaled over time: therefore, initial operationalization of the data space in local settings does not hinder potential upscaling of the data space post launch (enabling new participants or initiatives to be onboarded).</i></p> <p><i>The initial validity and usefulness of the methodology has been validated with the SILLs. As part of T2.4, through hands-on use of the methodology, we will further refine the approach.</i></p>

1.3. Deliverable Overview and Report Structure

The remainder of this deliverable is structured as follows:

- [Chapter 2](#) – presents the background for our work, describing literature on data spaces, business models and governance models.
- [Chapter 3](#) – presents the synthesis on governance models, existing tools, and mechanisms to enable the development of a dedicated tool for guiding design decisions on data space governance.
- [Chapter 4](#) – delineates the methodology, explaining how the approach has been developed through integrating the available tools.
- [Chapter 5](#) – details the approach, elaborating how and when design decisions on business modelling and governance for data spaces should be made.
- [Chapter 6](#) – specifies the conceptual background needed for the approach, listing the three perspectives (data space business models, application-specific business models and data space governance structure) for which design decisions should be made.
- [Chapter 7](#) – concludes this deliverable by listing potential next steps and limitations to our work.

References and an Appendix with illustrations of some of the tools are added.

2. Literature background

In this chapter, we detail the literature background used to design the proposed approach. First, we discuss the concepts of data sharing and data spaces and describe their value. Next, we describe the concept of international data spaces and the generic roles that are engaged for data spaces. Additionally, we elaborate on literature regarding business models (with increased emphasis on data-driven and FLW business models) as well as highlight literature on governance models used in practice. Each of these sections is concluded with a description of relevant tools and methods that can be considered to support business model or governance design decisions – we build upon these tools for the development of our approach.

2.1. Data sharing, data ecosystems and data spaces

In the past decades, as a result of digitization and technological change, the amount of data produced, exchanged and consumed has rapidly increased (Oliveira & Lóscio, 2018). Both public as well as private organisations often freely produce and use data to support new initiatives or to drive business activities, which sometimes transcends the boundaries of domains. Data can be considered as a public good or commodity and can be used as a means to create value. In light of this, we see the emergence of data ecosystems: complex networks of organisations (or actors) that exchange and use data as a main resource (Zuiderwijk et al., 2014). Typically, such ecosystems are established as a means to support, manage, and sustain new (data sharing) initiatives. On the basis of these initiatives, new business models and collaborations can be formed through data sharing and exchange.

A data space on the other hand is an emerging approach to data management which recognises that in large-scale integration scenarios (with thousands of data sources), it is difficult to obtain an upfront unifying schema across all sources (Curry, 2020). In other words, given the vast amount of data sources available (each with different characteristics, following different standards and adopting different ways of describing information), integration of data at organisations can pose a significant challenge given the likely heterogeneous nature of how data is presented and shared. Data spaces reduce this integration effort by leveraging automatic matching and mapping generation techniques. It provides an integrated means of searching, querying, updating and administering data for users of the data space (Curry, 2020). Therefore, regardless of format, location, or model, data can be managed, shared and integrated at organisations to facilitate value creation.

Data spaces should be differentiated from data markets: in a data market place, data sharing is not necessarily standardized to foster practices of integration, whereas many structures can exist in regards to how data sharing is coordinated (Muschalle et al., 2012). In a data marketplace, stakeholders can freely search for data that is offered which could help them in generating new value propositions or

provide data-driven services. A data marketplace can be characterized by monopolistic or oligopolistic players (i.e. those with significant market power) that provide data to generate profits.

2.1.1. International Data Space

International Data Spaces (IDS) enable the sovereign and self-determined exchange of data via a standardized connection across company boundaries (Pettenpohl et al., 2022). In the digitalized world, data sharing is becoming increasingly important, as the exchange and integration of data can enable participating parties to better support decision making, to align business activities and processes, foster new innovations or enable new services or business models. Having access to data therefore can be considered as a strategic asset. This is strongly aligned with the intentions of the EU as part of the Data Sharing Coalition: unlock the value of data by enabling organisations to share data across domains and sectors easily, calling for free movement of data, trust between stakeholders and organizations and fair use of data, see Figure 4 (Curry et al., 2022) However, data sharing as part of the data economy also poses significant challenges in terms of interoperability, transparency, trust, security and adaption by the critical mass (but also continuous improvements to sustain adoption) (Pettenpohl et al., 2022; Pitkänen & Luoma-Kyyny, 2022). Questions should be answered in regard to data ownership, data use and purpose of data sharing. As trust and transparency, particular in highly competitive business settings (such as logistics or manufacturing) is often difficult to establish, data sharing in such context is not self-evident (Dalmolen et al., 2018). Data spaces provide a data sharing infrastructure to overcome these barriers: it facilitates independent, yet controlled data sharing based on prespecified standards and protocols whilst maintaining data sovereignty for its data providers. Data therefore remains at its source and is only shared when needed (Pettenpohl et al., 2022).

Figure 4: The data sharing value wheel - pillars for European-governed data space (Curry et al., 2022)

Figure 5 presents an overview of the building blocks relevant to the design of data spaces. One can see that the building blocks at the bottom are decomposed into *technical and governance aspects* (for which the governance building blocks further include business and organizational aspects) highlighting the importance of these concepts in general as well as the synergy between them. As explained, although the technical building blocks are largely clear (further elaborated upon in the next section), the governance, and therefore also the business and organizational building blocks, lack explicit guidance on design decisions. This deliverable intends to address this gap.

Figure 5: Building blocks for data space solutions (OpenDEI, 2021)

2.1.1.1. Components of a data space

Elaborating on the technical architecture of the data space, the data space consists of the following components to enable data sharing and incorporate functionalities such as identity management, routing and analytics in order to do so (Cornelisse, 2022):

- Connector – supporting sovereignty of data for participants as well as providing the interface between participant and space ecosystem
- Security Gateway – supporting the secure transfer and exchange of data
- Broker – supporting the search and identification of suitable data
- Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service – enabling enrichment of identities of organisations and connectors with additional attributes
- Vocabulary Hub – supporting semantic interoperability for data sharing
- Clearing House – providing a set of clearing and settlement functions to support data sovereignty and data exchange transitions.
- App Store – promote the development of business ecosystem in which participants can develop software (services) (Pettenpohl et al., 2022).

An overview of how the components interact as part of the data space can be seen in Figure 6.

Figure 6: Overview of the structure and componentization of a data space (International Data Spaces Association, 2021)

2.1.1.2. Roles involved for data spaces

General roles included as part of a data space include *core participants, intermediary participants, software and service related roles* and *governance roles* (Pettenpohl et al., 2022) (Figure 7). Below, these roles are elaborated.

Figure 7: Data space roles and their interrelationships (OpenDEI, 2021)

Core participants

Core participants concern stakeholders that are involved or needed once data sharing takes place within a data space. These roles include data users, data providers, data owners and data consumers. Data owners exert control over the data, and can define how the data is used or who has access to this data. Data users on the other end of the spectrum use the data that they are allowed to access (given the usage policy of the data owner). In between the data owner and data user are the data provider and data consumer. Data providers transfer the data from the data owner, whereas data consumers receive the data transferred by the providers. Accordingly, data providers and data consumers form the 'bridge' between data owners and data users in data space. Logically, the exchange of data does call for incentives to do so as well as (in)formal agreements on how this data exchange is structured.

Intermediary participants

Roles involved for this category are related to metadata broker service providers (providing data access or data publishing options to core participants, as well as the ability to identify them), clearing house service providers (supervise transactions), app store developers (provide functions to support or use software services to use and/ or manage data), vocabulary providers (provide vocabularies to annotate and describe datasets) and identity providers (validate the identity of participants).

Software and service related roles

Software and service related roles provide software and service to participants of the data space. This category may entail app providers, service providers or software providers (Pettenpohl et al., 2022). Service providers support participants which do not have the technical infrastructure (for example an *Enterprise Resource Planning (ERP)* system or data sharing and management platform) required to share and exchange data as part of the data space. service providers therefore deploy (as-a-service) the required infrastructure for core participants to participate in the data space (and are often trusted parties for the data space). Additional services can be added (such as analysis, integration, cleaning) on top of the connectivity offered. Software providers in contrast do not provide services but rather engage in agreements with users (which can be core participants, but also, intermediary partners) on the exchange and use of software to support data exchange and integration operations.

Governance roles

The governance roles comprise of certification bodies and the association organising the data space (Pettenpohl et al., 2022). The role of the certification body is to ensure that both the components for the data space as well as its participants are certified (e.g., recognized as part of the data space). The association body generally promotes the development of the data space and governs the architecture deployed for the data space, as well as governs the general rulebook or standards employed for participating in the data space. To do so, support is needed from all previously defined roles.

2.1.1.3. Examples of International Data Spaces

Despite the novelty of data spaces as a concept, data space initiatives have already emerged in practice. In the following sections, we describe the purpose and working principles of some of these data space initiatives.

SCSN

Smart Connected Supplier Network (SCSN) is a data space initiative orchestrated in the Netherlands (and supported by the province of Noord-Brabant) to enable the exchange of data between manufacturing companies (<https://smart-connected.nl/nl>). These manufacturing companies range from large *Original Equipment Manufacturers* (OEMs) to smaller SMEs as well as steel producing companies. SCSN facilitates the automated receiving and sending of data needed in manufacturing supply chains, in which data sharing is critical for operations and supply decisions. Particularly (smaller) SMEs often lack the digital infrastructure to automate data integration as part of their daily practices, meaning data collection, interpretation and integration is often done manually (which takes time and is error prone). Through a one-time instance of connecting such SMEs to a SCSN service provider, SMEs can become part of SCSN and can automate data exchange and sharing. The governance mechanisms at SCSN enable SMEs to dictate to whom data is exchanged to – SMEs therefore remain owner of their data (often a key concern in manufacturing industries).

SCSN emerged through the innovation program 'Fabriek van de Toekomst', aimed at sharing resources (such as products, facilities, but also data) to improve the innovativeness and effectiveness of manufacturing companies. To move past initial piloting of data sharing solutions (and to strive for long-term applications), the need was recognized to form an independent foundation to manage the data space (SCSN). This included clear decisions on how governance was structured (rulebook) and how organizations would collaborate for the data space. Through subsequent scaling the number of organizations involved, additional value propositions could be enabled.

As an already fully operational data space, SCSN has dealt with questions regarding organizational and data governance. Accordingly, several documents have been drafted to explicate what governance mechanisms are in play to support data sharing for the data space. As a result, documents such as the *House Rules* as well as *Contractual agreement for Service Providers* (available at their website) have been drafted to govern participation for SCSN. These documents detail aspects such as the rules of participation, the legal form by which SCSN is governed, agreements on how revenues are shared, penalty and reward mechanisms in play to govern interactions for the data space.

FENIX

FENIX is a Connecting Europe Facility project with the aim to establish a federated architecture for data sharing between European logistics organisations, such as shippers, logistic service providers, mobility infrastructure providers, cities and authorities (<https://fenix-network.eu/>). The goal is to work to support the long-term interoperability between existing and future platforms in the context of logistics, such that data can be exchanged and shared by transport and logistics operators. It intends to overcome the fragmented systems (which lack connectivity *between* systems) supporting logistic decision making. In doing so, common protocols are defined for data sharing service whereas a horizontal collaboration between service providers and platforms is to be established to harmonize services that are offered and enable data sharing.

GAIA-X

Gaia-X is a European initiative that develops a software framework of control and governance, implementing a common set of policies and rules (to be applied to cloud/edge technology) such that interoperability, portability and controllability of data and services can be obtained between these technologies (<https://gaia-x.eu/>). This is with the intention to support European organisations in terms of their competitiveness by means of providing a sovereign, transparent digital ecosystem. Note that Gaia-X does not intend to become a cloud service provider itself or a cloud management platform: it intends to provide the architecture by which open interfaces for data sharing are established and for which common standards and policies are installed to support data sharing. Service providers consequently which adopt the Gaia-X standard can create, operate or adopt services operated for Gaia-X. It is the intention that these services are not necessarily limited to a certain domain but can be used as part of cross-sector support to create value from data (sharing).

Implications for business models and governance

From the above examples of data spaces, we can conclude that data space initiatives can come to market following different trajectories and can address different value propositions: in the case of SCSN, the initiative emerged through collective action of the stakeholders involved, establishing a foundation to support the long-term exploitation of the data space. In contrast, FENIX and GAIA-X are initiatives driven by the European Union, orchestrated as a result of long-term policy making to sustain and improve the competitiveness of (organizations within) Europe. This influences both the type of business models that should be considered for the data space as well as the appropriate governance structure: for the former (SCSN) the instigating stakeholders formed a foundation to support long-term data space operations and intent to connect the data space over time to other initiatives; for the latter, the intent is to create federated data spaces, after which each data space can determine how the governance should be structured (whilst maintaining compatibility with other data spaces).

2.2. Business models and business model design

The business model concept has received significant attention in both practice and research over the last two decades, although diverse interpretations of the concept exist (Dasilva & Trkman, 2014). In this deliverable, we consider a business model as *'the logic through which a (network of) organisation(s) intend(s) to create value for its end-user or customer, and through which it is able to capture value in return'* (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010). As such, a business model should be led by a central value proposition for its intended users or customers, and should delineate how (in terms of activities, competencies and resources that are deployed) organisation(s) intend(s) to establish and provide this value proposition.

Business models are strongly related to business strategy (Magretta, 2002; Shafer et al., 2005): a business model should fulfil (part of) the business strategy, meaning that it should satisfy one or more strategic objectives that an organisation aims to achieve. In addition, business models provide the context for new technologies or innovations, explaining how such innovations contribute to value creation and how they should be embedded for the current business logic (Veit et al., 2014). Business models therefore have a pivotal role in aligning the organisational business strategy to its business processes, resources and information systems (Al-Debei & Avison, 2010).

Traditionally, business models have been designed from a *resource-based, organisation-centric perspective*: emphasis is placed on (the design of) the key resources, activities and relationships needed to create value for a specific customer segment or group (Bankvall et al., 2017; Kullak et al., 2021). Widely used in practice and research, the Business Model Canvas (BMC) (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010) is a

prime example of this: the BMC (Figure 8) is a template consisting of nine interrelated building blocks that can be used for the design of business models from the perspective of a *single* organisation.

Figure 8: Template for the Business Model Canvas (Osterwalder & Pigneur, 2010)

Although the contributions and relationships to other partners in the ecosystem or business network are considered, the organisational perspective remains the focal point of interest. In contrast, we also see that other business model design techniques are developed to accommodate the design of business models that take an explicit networked view. For example, the Service-Dominant Business Model Radar or SDBM/R (Turetken et al., 2019), given its circular design, enables the design of networked business models, emphasizing value co-creation through collaboration / collaborative use of resources. A template of the SDBM/R is illustrated in Figure 9. Starting from the co-created value-in-use at the centre (defining the *value* that is ultimately created in collaboration with end-users or customers), users of the tool can explore what roles and individual value propositions should be included to provide this value-in-use. These roles can be linked to concrete stakeholders, after which activities to be conducted as well as costs and benefits for the business model can be mapped.

Figure 9: Template for the Service-Dominant Business Model Radar (Turetken et al., 2019)

2.2.1. Data-driven business models

In the context of digital transformation and digitalization, we see that business models are increasingly considered as a means to explain, structure or support data-driven innovations and initiatives: through business models, decision makers aim to explicate how such data-driven initiatives can create value for end-users and how these should be supported or embedded for the business logic. The resulting *data-driven* business models therefore rely on data as the main resource for value creation (Kühne & Böhmman, 2018).

In the modern era, many successful data-driven business models exist, using data to great effect to provide digital services and to offer customized value propositions to end-users. Often, organisations leverage platforms as a means to provide these digital services and use these platforms to collect data on users to further enhance and improve upon these services (Guggenberger et al., 2020). We see that in the current market a plethora of platform businesses exist: well-known examples are platform services such as Facebook, Netflix or Uber, in which these organisations act as a platform service provider and collect data on the behaviour and interactions of users on the platform. On the basis of this user data, services are continuously improved or enhanced or additional services are offered.

Although data-driven business models clearly have significant potential for value creation, there are also challenges towards the use of data in data-driven business models. In light of data sovereignty and data privacy, it is important that the use of data towards value creation is transparent and clear: it should be explicated to

customers or end-users how their data is collected and how this data is used (Kühne & Böhmman, 2019; Stolwijk et al., 2022). This is where practices of governance on collaboration and data sharing are important.

In light of the emergence and deployment of data ecosystems in which organisations collaboratively share data to provide new products and services, we observe that the interest in *data ecosystem* or *data space* business models is vastly increasing (Kitsios et al., 2017). These business models explain how data is shared between governments, public and / or private organisations can enable or enhance new value creation or foster the provisioning of new data-driven services. Previous research has focused on the identification of actors in data ecosystem business models, identifying actor roles, amongst others, such as data providers, service providers, users and application developers, as well as the mechanisms used to guide or drive collaboration between actors in data ecosystem business models (Kitsios et al., 2017; Otto & Jarke, 2019). One can immediately observe that these roles have overlap with the general roles identified for data spaces (see Section 2.1.1.2). However, for data spaces, clear roles regarding certification, clearing house service providers and metadata brokers are additionally included.

In addition, such data ecosystems can also be used as a means to strengthen or streamline communication within current supply chains, to foster transparency and to empower supply chain stakeholders (Jonak et al., 2019). This can consequently serve to improve business-customer relationships or to drive new value propositions. For example, data generation at various supply chain partners can help in aligning business activities across the value chain and reduce inefficiencies or communication barriers for the production process. It could also contribute towards the facilitation of sustainable (ecological, environmental) value propositions to customers (offering transparency but also traceability on how a certain product or solution is produced (Egels-Zandén & Hansson, 2016)). However, such data ecosystems do not necessarily provide success on their own: in addition to technological support, buy-in from supply chain actors to share and integrate data, as well as collaboration with research organisations and legislators is needed to foster the value of integrated or transformed data (Jonak et al., 2019). It should therefore be clear what value propositions can be established through the (meaningful) use and sharing of data. This highlights the importance of business model thinking in terms of data-driven services and data sharing.

2.2.2. Sustainable and collaborative business models

Traditionally, business models have been used as a vehicle to drive profit generation: new business models should primarily be (financially) profitable and contribute to the bottom line of an organisation (Morris et al., 2005). However, we see that this perspective is rapidly changing as organisations increasingly recognize

the need to contribute to society and our environment. As a result, we see the increased interest in the design and development of *sustainable* business models that address the double (Wilburn & Wilburn, 2014) or even the triple bottom line (Boons & Lüdeke-Freund, 2013; Short et al., 2013): business models that emphasize value creation along the pillars of financial, social and environmental value. Many examples of *sustainable business models* exist, particularly those that target waste and emissions reduction, aimed at synergizing environmental and financial value. This can be considered as a complementary value proposition (e.g., the company *Displate* that plants a tree for each metallic painting that is bought by a customer) or can be the direct result of using a service or embedded as part of the value chain (e.g., the FutureCraftLoop brand by Adidas – shoes that are constructed from recycled material and can be brought back to Adidas to be recycled once more).

In close connection with striving for sustainability, the concept of *collaborative* business models is increasingly becoming more prevalent in research and practice. In a collaborative business model, mutual value creation and capture is key, meaning that all network actors involved should be able to reap the benefits of (participation in) a new business model (Rohrbeck et al., 2013). This is in contrast with the traditional notion of business models which emphasize profit maximization, which inherently means that some actors will be better off than others, but also at the expense of others. As collaborative business models strive for mutual value creation (or value co-creation), these models inherently address building synergies or long-term relationships with partners (Maglio & Spohrer, 2013), serving as a valuable starting point for achieving sustainability. Many private-public partnerships are built upon collaborative principles, finding a business logic that creates value for both types of parties involved even though strategic concerns may differ significantly (profit-driven versus social or environmental-driven). Such collaborations however require clear governance structures to generate trust to do so: this integration between collaborative business modelling and governance structures (i.e. how do design decisions for collaborative business models influence governance structures and vice-versa) is still ill-defined. Guiding support (in terms of a design approach catered to configuring collaborative business models and associated governance structures) is needed here, both in general as well as in the context of ZeroW, in which it is the goal to reduce social inequalities and ensure fair income for all actors involved (through mutual value capture) as part of the sustainable transition.

2.2.3. Business models in the context of FLW

In terms of business models directed at the reduction of FLW, some examples are introduced in literature. Ciccullo et al. (2022) describe the Food Cloud's business model. Food Cloud aims to reduce FLW by operating as a digital platform provider.

On this platform, Food Cloud matches organisations in the food supply chain (such as retailers, restaurants or producers) to local charities and communities with the goal to redistribute surplus food, taking into account characteristics such as geographical location, products offered, and quantity offered. Based on what is offered, local charities and communities (if meeting the criteria) can respond to any surplus food available on the platform.

A similar business model to the Food Cloud solution is discussed by Matzembacher et al. (2021). Focusing on FLW reduction in Brazil, it is observed that in the food supply chain a significant amount of waste is generated due to products lacking the proper aesthetics. To reduce this food waste, a platform solution is introduced that connects food producers and retailers to customers on 'secondary markets'. Here, the products that aesthetically cannot be offered on the primary markets or products that are close to the expiry date are offered at reduced prices. Customers (ranging from private customers to restaurants) can then select what products they wish to purchase, following a similar process as for the primary markets.

Ribeiro et al. (2018) discuss the business model of Fruta Feia ('Ugly Fruit') active in Portugal. Similarly, to the previous model, Fruta Feia (a non-profit cooperative) intends to reduce food waste as a result of vegetables and fruit lacking the correct aesthetics. The business model of Fruta Feia is that they buy such left-over products directly from the farmers (such that the farmers are still compensated for their efforts) and consequently sells these fruits and vegetables to consumers through standardized delivery points in cities in which they participate (at lower tariffs than what is typically the case for fruits and vegetables offered in regular supermarkets). The business model strongly relies on building personal relationships with farmers and consumers of the food products: as a result, the delivery points are often informal in nature and catered to the characteristics of the neighbourhood and for which the social community aspect is stressed. Transportation of left-over fruits and vegetables is handled by Fruta Feia.

Moving away from cases explicitly documented in academic literature, the organisation SpoilerAlert (<https://www.spoileralert.com/>) offers a software-based solution to retailers and food producers that on the one hand collects insights on the current inventory position of a respective retailer / food producer (particularly in regards to the expiration date of these products) and on the other hand offers a marketplace on which interested retailers can respond to (close to expiry date products). In this way, the solution provides data-driven insights to retailers on what products are valuable to offer on second-hand markets as they otherwise will have to be destroyed or thrown away. This can help improve inventory management at retailers and contribute towards sustainable business changes. Furthermore, the platform serves as the communication hub for finding connected, interested buyers (at a discounted price) or charity organisations to avoid food waste.

Contrastingly, the organisation Winnow offers a software-based solution that helps restaurants to digitally document food waste as a result of cooking or kitchen activities. Use of the solution is simple: it calls upon kitchen staff to document what food they throw away, its amount and under what circumstances. This data is captured, analysed and transformed through a dashboard type interface, providing insights to decision makers on how food waste can be reduced.

2.2.4. Business modelling tools

Several methods and tools exist in practice to support the process of (collaborative) business modelling. As our approach should support design decision making on business models, both from a data space perspective as well as an application-specific perspective, these methods and tools can serve as an important basis to do so. In the following section, we describe the use of the collaborative business modelling process proposed as part of the H2020 Ploutos project (Berkers et al., 2022). Additionally, we describe how reference business models can be used to support design decisions for data space business models as well as application-specific business models.

2.2.4.1.1. Collaborative Business Modelling Process (Ploutos)

The collaborative business modelling process proposed as part of H2020 Ploutos offers a structured, set-wise approach to help stakeholders design and evaluate their business models (Berkers et al., 2022). This process builds upon the principles of collaborative business modelling (Rohrbeck et al., 2013): value creation and capture should be distributed equally over stakeholders involved. An overview of this process is illustrated in Figure 10. One can see that the process consists of six practical workshops that address different concerns or aspects of business modelling:

Figure 10: Collaborative business modelling process supported through practical workshops (Berkers et al., 2022)

1. The first workshop consists of understanding what value propositions are enabled by means of a new solution, technology or service. It forces users of the process to think about the relevancy of the new solution as well as to think about what customers or end-users will be targeted. It is important that this is understood early on, as it drives decision making on other aspects of the business model design (such as the network to include, the revenue model to select or the business logic to be adopted).

2. The second workshop explores the technical architecture of the proposed solution in terms of what data, knowledge or information is to be collected. This is structured by means of the DAMIAN tool (Berkers et al., 2014). This tool provides a template to map and make explicit how data is collected (i.e. through sensors, manual, other) and how this data is consequently used to create value for end-users). The value proposition(s) identified in workshop 1 should be enabled by means of this data collection. Logically, any mismatch should be resolved, either by tweaking the value proposition or by collecting additional information. This tool also makes explicit what roles or activities are needed for the business model design to do so (for example, a stakeholder is able to provide sensors to support data collection). In addition to the technical background, this workshop also focuses on mapping the *value creation process* or customer journey: how will end-users or customers use the proposed solution? What activities are introduced or what will end-users have to do differently? How will this affect value capture? The value creation process also sheds light on what stakeholders should be involved. This serves as an input for understanding the network of stakeholders to be included as part of business model design.
3. The third workshop focuses on drafting a (preliminary) business model design, using the inputs generated through the previous workshops. Using the SDBM/R, the stakeholders, value propositions and identified business logic can be mapped. This should help in determining whether additional stakeholders should be added to support the central value proposition(s). In this workshop, design decisions on value capture (e.g. revenue models or investment decisions) should also be made.
4. The fourth workshop explores how the business model design is operationalized and how it contributes to achieving long-term objectives. As part of this workshop, scaling intentions are considered: the current business model design should be equipped to support these intentions long-terms. As a result, important implicit assumptions, challenges and barriers can be identified. These barriers can serve as input for adjusting the business model design (generated through the previous workshop) or can be tackled through collaborative action.
5. The fifth workshop serves as the formal evaluation of the business model design. This may involve both a quantitative evaluation (understanding whether each stakeholder captures sufficient, in the eyes of the beholder, value) as well as a qualitative evaluation of the business model, addressing aspects such as the *robustness, viability or feasibility* of the business model (Gilsing et al., 2020). This workshop should generate formal commitment of stakeholders to pursue the proposed business model design, or provide input for further business model (re)design and concretization.

6. The sixth workshop concludes the collaborative business modelling process, identifying concrete next steps towards realizing the business model. Note that during the operation of the business model, changes may occur which were previously unaccounted for: as a result, previous steps of the process can be revisited.

To support business modelling as part of the approach in this deliverable, we will build upon this process. Accordingly, applications for the data space (OFLW) can use this process to understand what value propositions are enabled by means of the data space and what business models can be designed to support these applications. In Chapter 5, we will further elaborate on the use of this process for the approach. In Appendix A of this deliverable, some business model examples which have emerged through use of the application have been presented.

2.2.4.1.2. Reference business models to support design of new business models

In addition to the Ploutos process, users can also leverage *reference business models* to support design decisions. Such a reference business model highlights important generic roles and value propositions that can be included. Consequently, concrete stakeholders can be mapped against these generic roles and value propositions. Accordingly, reference business models serve as a starting point for business model design, both for data space business models as well as application-specific business models (business models enabled through data spaces).

For data spaces, we see that general functions expected relate to *identification, authentication, connectivity, service authorisation and clearing house services*. Such services should be included as part of the data space in order for the data space to 'function'. If we would consider all services to be offered by an individual organization, this means that for any data space, a broker service provider, identity provider, app store provider and vocabulary provider should be included. Very rarely it would be the case that single organisation can provide all required services, hence these generic roles can be mapped to concrete stakeholders for a given initiative to aid business model design.

Accordingly, an example reference data space business model design is illustrated in Figure 11 (represented by means of the SDBM/R).

Figure 11: Reference data space business model design

One can see that data providers, service providers and data users are included as part of the design, being important in terms of the provisioning (data providers), connectivity (service providers) or usage (data users) of data. The data space moreover requires an orchestrator (in purple): the reference business model considers as starting point that any alliance structure can be positioned here. Depending on what concrete alliance structure is selected as part of developing a new data space, this role can be further defined.

It should be noted that multiple roles logically can be fulfilled by a single stakeholder: for example, certification as well as clearing house activities can reside within a single concrete stakeholders. Nonetheless, for business model design, it is important to verify whether these roles need to be included or defined, are fulfilled, and by which actor(s).

Similarly, for application-specific business models, reference models can be developed. Building upon the cases described in 2.2.3, a reference model as presented in Figure 12 can be proposed. One can see that generic roles such as a consumer of 2nd class food (or food close to expiry date) as well as a producer of food (wishing to reduce FLW) are included. Generally, a service or platform provider role is included to facilitate the interconnection and exchange of data between these parties. In the context of data spaces, this service provider would need to be an active participant in a data space to do so. Often, transporters or distributors are needed to get the food from A to B. Once these generic roles are mapped to

concrete stakeholders, SILLs can use this reference model as a starting point for (application-specific) business model design, also focusing on the concrete costs and benefits that are captured as a result of the new FLW initiative.

Figure 12: Reference business model for FLW initiatives

2.3. Governance models

Governance models help in defining clear guidelines, responsibilities and accountability in managing organisations or in supporting decision making (Weber et al., 2009). Governance models are a system of rules and structures applicable to objects, organisations and can even be imposed on organisations (for example in the context of governmental governance) (Brooks & Cullinane, 2006). In the context of data spaces, governance models can be related to *organisational or ecosystem governance* (focused on rules regarding how participants collaborate or what participants are allowed within the data space) as well as *data governance* (focused on rules regarding how data is exchanged and managed) (Otto, 2022). Logically, both types of models are different in terms of the rules set as they address different objects of governance. For example, (data) governance models in the context of open data dictate that open data should be *complete, primary, timely, accessible, machine processable, non-discriminatory, non-proprietary, permanent, license-free* and (preferably) *free-of-charge* (Welle Donker & van Loenen, 2016), enabling organisations (private or public) to *govern* what type of data should be generated, what form it should take or what data can be considered as *open data*. Conversely, organisations can also *govern* how data is exchanged between *partnering*

organisations, or what organisations can access certain information. Organisational governance can also determine how new initiatives are institutionalized: for example, joint ventures can be established as part of the formation of new data spaces, driving the development and promotion of the data space in practice (Otto, 2022). This calls for organisational governance, next to data governance, dictating how organisations collaborate (organisational governance) and how organisations share data (data governance). Logically, rules and mechanisms for both types of governance can then differ, but both are needed to support data-driven initiatives. Therefore, in the context of data spaces, emphasis should be placed on (supporting the design of) both organisational as well as data governance.

Research has investigated what type of aspects can be considered in terms of data as well as organisational governance. In the following section, we detail what attributes exist for both governance types and what generic models can be considered.

2.3.1. Data governance

Data governance is the exercise of authority and control over the management of data (Abraham et al., 2019). It intends to maximize the value of data and to manage data-related risks (DAMA International, 2009). It specifies decision rights and accountabilities for organisation’s decision making about its data. It also includes formalized policies, standards, procedures, to facilitate data exchange and to monitor compliance (Abraham et al., 2019). Generally, data sharing and management should adhere to the FAIR guiding principles: data should be *findable*, *accessible*, *interoperable* and *reusable* (Wilkinson et al., 2016). These principles are presented in detail in Figure 13. To ensure that these principles can be upheld, data governance mechanisms should be in place.

To be findable
F1. (Meta)data is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier
F2. Data is described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below)
F3. Metadata clearly and explicitly includes the identifier of the data it describes
F4. (Meta)data is registered or indexed in a searchable resource
To be accessible
A1. (Meta)data is retrievable by their identifier using a standardised communications protocol
A1.1 The protocol is open, free, and universally implementable
A1.2 The protocol allows for an authentication and authorisation procedure, where necessary
A2. Metadata is accessible, even when the data is no longer available
To be interoperable
I1. (Meta)data uses a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation
I2. (Meta)data uses vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
I3. (Meta)data includes qualified references to other (meta)data
To be reusable
R1. (Meta)data is richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
R1.1. (Meta)data is released with a clear and accessible data usage license
R1.2. (Meta)data is associated with detailed provenance
R1.3. (Meta)data meets domain-relevant community standards

Figure 13: FAIR guiding principles for data management (Wilkinson et al., 2016)

In addition to the FAIR principles, data sharing and exchange should be secure in nature to stimulate trust. Figure 14 presents an overview of the important trends related to data security. It goes without saying that data governance mechanisms should address these concerns as part of data spaces.

In the following, some important trends with an impact on data security:

- 1** The interdependency between societal processes and information systems increases
- 2** New interdependencies between organisations and the state emerge
- 3** Information security issues become more international
- 4** Needs to manage private or confidential information and public appearances in ICT environments increase
- 5** Protection of personal data becomes a considerable political issue
- 6** It becomes increasingly difficult to ensure the correctness of information
- 7** The correctness of information becomes increasingly important
- 8** Data gathering increases
- 9** Data combination from different sources increases
- 10** Traceability of persons and goods increases
- 11** Malicious action against information systems increases
- 12** Quality and security issues are increasingly taken into account in software development
- 13** Automation/autonomous systems are increasingly employed to effect security
- 14** Availability of information increases as the public information resources are opened
- 15** Commercial interests drive actors to restrict access to proprietary information resources
- 16** Governance of access to information resources in organisations becomes more difficult

*Figure 14: data security trends which should be addressed by means of data governance
(Pitkänen & Luoma-Kyyny, 2022)*

Abraham et al. (2019) identify 3 mechanisms to data governance (see Figure 15): structural mechanisms, procedural mechanisms and relational mechanisms. Note that these mechanisms also include discussions on roles and responsibilities (related to organisational governance) which should be shared in terms of data governance: this highlights the need for an integrated perspective on organisational and data governance.

Structural mechanisms entail identifying or understanding of the roles and responsibilities required for data management, as well as the allocation of decision making authority for the roles defined (Borgman et al., 2016). Roles can vary between defining data governance leaders or councils or by identifying data owners, data producers and data consumers (e.g. roles that concern either how data is produced, how data management is monitored or how data is consumed or owned). As explained, in the context of data spaces, these roles can refer to organisations that take part for the data space (initiative). Next, based on the roles, decision making authority is allocated, which mandates, who can take which actions related to data governance (Khatri & Brown, 2010). Here, the distinction can be made between hierarchical positioning of decision making authority, functional

positioning, or a positioning of authority based on a spectrum from centralized to decentralized decision making (Weber et al., 2009). For data spaces, particularly the latter perspective on decision making is important: data spaces strive for sovereignty of data, aim for a level-playing field in terms of data sharing and exchange, and call for *decentralised or federated* data architecture to support this. Therefore, these decision rights should remain at the principle owners of the data.

Figure 15: Data governance mechanisms (Abraham et al., 2019)

In terms of procedural mechanisms, the following mechanisms are identified: *policies, standards, data strategy, processes, procedures, contracts, performance measurement, compliance monitoring and issue management* (Abraham et al., 2019). These represent the set of options available to ensure that data is recorded accurately, used effectively, held securely (where applicable) and shared appropriately (Borgman et al., 2016).

- The data strategy dictates objectives to be achieved by means of data sharing and management (for example, sharing data to counteract FLW). It also includes how business continuity should be fostered and how risks towards this continuity should be addressed.
- Policies provide guidelines on how data is created, stored, shared or exchanged.
- (Data) standards on the other hand relate to how the data is represented and governed and ensure consistency across organisations, ecosystems or data spaces (DAMA International, 2009).

- Procedures relate to explaining how (in terms of steps, methods) data management or data sharing activities are conducted.
- Contracts are used to formalize agreements between organisations sharing or providing data. Such contracts can related to Service Level Agreements (SLAs) or data sharing agreements (DSAs) (Abraham et al., 2019), describing how organisations intend to collaborate or interact and what happens in cases of failure to comply.
- Performance measurement or performance measures help in assessing the extent to which the objectives set for data governance are satisfied or achieved.
- Compliance monitoring intends to track and enforce whether compliance or conformance to policies, procedures, contracts and standards set is upheld (DAMA International, 2009)
- Lastly, issue management supports the resolution of issues identified for data management practices and helps in escalation management where needed (DAMA International, 2009).

Relational mechanisms entail practices of *communication, training and coordination of decision making* (Borgman et al., 2016). Here, communication refers to generating awareness on data governance plans for stakeholders involved, whereas training ensures that stakeholders have the necessary knowledge and qualifications to support practices for data governance. Lastly, coordination of decision making defines practices of how alignment or cooperation between stakeholders is achieved (for example through committees, integrator roles or working groups).

What data governance model is appropriate depends significantly on the context in which it is considered. Figure 16 illustrates that depending on the goals and combination of governance mechanisms, different governance models can be formed (Zygmuntowski et al., 2021). For example, in cases for which the governance mechanism is based on the distribution of rights, whereas the goals are organization-specific (private / growth driven), personal data sovereignty is strived to protect how data is shared. Alternatively, in the case of trust-based, public driven initiatives, governance models take the form of public data commons in which data is shared openly to create common services for all.

		STAKEHOLDER CONTROL / GOVERNANCE MECHANISMS	
		INDIVIDUAL / RIGHTS-BASED	INSTITUTIONAL / TRUST-BASED
VALUE ALLOCATION / GOVERNANCE GOALS	PRIVATE / GROWTH-DRIVEN	Personal data sovereignty	Data collaboratives
	PUBLIC / WELFARE-DRIVEN	Data cooperatives	Public data commons

Figure 16: Data governance models and governance goals (Zygmuntowski et al., 2021)

In terms of data governance for collective goods, several challenges have to be overcome (see Figure 17). Challenges to motivate action on data governance can relate to the fact that actors struggle to perceive the value or need for data governance. Additionally, actors can remain committed to existing collaborations or business practices rather than to work towards new forms of collaboration and to shape data governance. Lastly, actors can be constrained by current competencies or capabilities (for example in sharing or using data) to engage in data sharing. As a result, they are not aware of why data governance is needed.

#	Challenge	Data governance	Collective action in IS
1	Perceiving value	Actors struggle to perceive the value creating potential of data or data governance (Begg and Caira 2012)	Participants attribute different meanings to collective good produced based on their ideological positions (Constantinides and Barrett 2015)
2	Enabling collaboration	Actors remain committed to group-specific or individual functions rather than organization-wide development (Vilminko-Heikkinen et al. 2016)	Participants compromise or obscure greater, collective outcomes to protect or realize individual, short-term interests (Markus et al. 2006)
3	Fostering capabilities	Actors are constrained by lack of skills or competences in handling data as a resource (Thompson et al. 2015)	Quality of good produced depends on the sustained contribution of (heterogenous) resources by participants (Mindel et al. 2018; Monge et al. 1998)

Figure 17: Preliminary challenges identified for data governance for collective goods (Benfeldt et al., 2020)

2.3.2. Organisational governance

Organisational governance concerns the rules, procedures, decision making rights and responsibility that drive the continuity of organisations and protect stakeholders associated to the organisation (Klein et al., 2019). In contrast to data governance, it concerns the structure by which organisations (rather than data) are managed and monitored, and who is responsible for what decisions for the organisation. Organisational governance can concern both *intra-organisational governance* as well as *inter-organisational governance* (van den Broek & van Veenstra, 2015): in the context of data spaces, the latter is particularly important, as it dictates how organisations cooperate or collaborate with another ecosystem or initiative. However, the former may influence how decision making for an organisation is structured and thus affect the organisation's compatibility or acceptance to participate in a data sharing initiative. Logically, *inter-organisational governance* also has strong ties with what strategic collaboration form or organisational structure is

selected (Todeva & Knoke, 2005). Organisations can form, for example, joint ventures by which two or more organisations create a new (legal) organisation to promote or support the development of a new initiative. Alternatively, collaborations or alliances can be in the form of licensing agreements in which an organisation grants the right to other organisations to use data or technologies. Similarly, organisational collaboration can be structured hierarchically (organisations have more or full control through ownership as a result of acquisition or mergers) or can take the form of cooperatives in which (typically smaller) organisations combine, coordinate and manage their collective resources (Todeva & Knoke, 2005). Each of these alliance forms has implications for how governance is structured: in case of hierarchical relationships (subsidiaries versus parent), decision making rights resides at the parents, whereas for cooperatives shared responsibilities and decision making rights are expected. (de Man & Luvison, 2019; Todeva & Knoke, 2005)..

An example of how building alliances shapes organizational governance is illustrated through Figure 18. This case concerns the governance of the alliance established between KLM and Northwest.

One can see that to shape the organizational governance between both partners, several elements of organizational governance had to be addressed, such as understanding the goal of the alliance, the legal form by which the alliance is shaped as well as how decision-making rights are distributed. These elements (e.g., goal, legal form, financial agreements, scope, decision making, governance bodies, communication structure, culture and trust) are also important to consider in the context of governing new data spaces: it should be clear what purpose is fulfilled by means of the data space as well as what governance mechanisms are selected to generate trust or to distribute decision making.

Figure 1 Governance structure of the virtual joint venture between KLM and Northwest, 1997–present.

Table 1 Alliance governance in the KLM–Northwest alliance after 1997.	
Governance element	Example from the KLM–Northwest alliance
Goal	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase revenue by combining networks and exchanging passengers • KLM operates flights in Europe, Middle East and Africa; Northwest operates flights in North America
Legal form	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contractual
Financial agreements	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fifty–fifty profit sharing
Scope and exclusivity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • North Atlantic route • Exclusive
Decision-making	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consensus
Governance bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Alliance Steering Committee • Five working groups
Communication structure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Multiple points of contacts • Use of informal channels
Culture	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Continuous communication to align the two businesses
Trust/commitment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ten year contract • Closing down of sales offices signals commitment • Social events to build personal relationships • Personal unions on a board level and inside the companies

Figure 18: Organizational governance to manage alliance between KLM and Northwest (de Man et al., 2010)

2.4. Integrating data governance and organisational governance

Lis & Otto (2020) make explicit for both intra-organisational settings as well as inter-organisational settings (see Figure 19) what differences exist between both settings in terms of data governance: for inter-organisational settings, the emphasis of data governance lies on achieving collaboration between organisations and facilitating data sharing to achieve common goals or value propositions.

Characteristic	Intra-organizational Data Governance	Inter-organizational Data Governance
Scope	- Internal (within an organization e.g. departments and business areas)	- External between organizations or ecosystem (e.g. platform, business partner, customer)
Purpose	- Ensure the provision of decision rights and accountabilities for the management and use of data. - Set up organizational structures and use governance mechanisms to improve data quality, manage resources across a single organization and formalize guidelines for data resources (Abraham et al. 2019)	- Establishment of governance mechanisms that foster collaboration between multiple entities - Facilitate data sharing under consideration of data ownership, access, integration and usage - Ensuring that each participant contributes in pursuing common goals and value propositions (de Prieëlle et al. 2020)
Goals	- Establish strategic importance of data as an asset on corporate level - Maximize the value of data for the organization by improving the quality of decision-making - Establishment of clearly designated roles for data elements (Otto 2015; Weber et al. 2009)	- Creation of an ecosystem with aligned balance of control and authority to incentive data sharing and value creation among actors (Oliveira et al. 2019) - Adherence to fair overarching rules that protect the interests of ecosystem partners while overcoming conflicts (Otto and Jarke 2019)
Roles and Organization	- Designated data roles, councils or committees within the organization e.g. data owner, data steward, chief data officer (Korhonen et al. 2013) - Organization anchored within hierarchal structures of the organization (Otto 2011)	- Depending on the activities, an organization can embrace different roles e.g. data provider, data broker, infrastructure provider (Oliveira et al. 2019) - Different modes of organization are possible depending on the conceptualization of the ecosystem in technical or sociotechnical aspects (de Prieëlle et al. 2020)
Modes	- Centrally organized with uniform approach for all internal business units - Decentral approach for more responsibility and autonomy within business unit - federal or hybrid approach combining the governance approaches (Brown 1997; Sambamurthy and Zmud 1999)	- Distributed and decentral (Otto and Jarke 2019) - Shared, lead, or networked governance (Provan and Kenis 2008) - Market, bazaar, hierarchy, network governance (Van den Broek and Van Veenstra 2015) - Platform governance (Schreieck et al. 2016; Tiwana 2014; Lee et al. 2017)
Governance instruments	- Structural, procedural, relational mechanisms manifested within the organization (Abraham et al. 2019; De Haes and Wim Van Grembergen 2004; Tallon et al. 2013)	- Regulatory instruments, licenses, formal contract-based agreements, technical measures for data integration and usage policies, data sharing agreements (Otto and Jarke 2019)

Figure 19: Characteristics of intra-organisational versus inter-organisational data governance (Lis & Otto, 2020)

To do so, an ecosystem of balanced control and authority (to incentivise data sharing) should be established. This calls for overarching rules that protect participants but also help in dealing with conflicts (Otto & Jarke, 2019). Design principles to facilitate managing the commons (i.e., what jointly is used or owned) are the following and can help in driving policy making for data spaces (Ostrom, 1990):

1. Commons should have clearly defined boundaries (who can access what?)
2. Rules should be fit within specific contexts or 'local' circumstances
3. Decision making should be participatory (users, stakeholders should have some form of decision making power)
4. Rules set for commons should be upheld and accounted for
5. Mechanisms should be in place to penalize abuse of commons
6. Conflict resolution should be straightforward and accessible
7. Commons (rights) should be legitimate and recognized
8. Commons should be nested in larger ecosystems

Such principles should be taken into account for the development of data spaces. The practical framework proposed by Bloom et al. (2021) can be used to assess to

what extent the design principles have been upheld for a new data space or data sharing initiative and what design questions should be asked to adhere to the principles stated above: it offers 'maturity' levels on how well design principles have already been addressed. An overview of this framework can be found at the Mozilla Foundation (Bloom et al., 2021).

Roles identified can be covered by different organisations. Here, *organisational governance structures* can be selected, such as setting up a joint venture, cooperatives or other forms of collaboration. Based on this, decision rights regarding *data governance* can be defined, which can be shared, lead or networked (Provan & Kenis, 2008), for which variants of governance structures can be selected (van den Broek & van Veenstra, 2015):

- Marketplaces: contractual exchange of data
- Hierarchy: data exchange is governed by an authority or dominant parties
- Bazaar: exchange of data based on data quality
- Alliance or network: trust-based exchange of data

Consequently, coordination and governance mechanisms are associated to this: market places build upon contracts for data exchange, for which ownership remains at or is transferred to individual organisations. For bazaars, coordination happens based on data quality, for which all organisations become owner of the data that is shared (open data). In hierarchy settings, power is exerted by dominant parties / authorities for the network, which also determine who attains ownership of data. In networked settings, trust is employed as coordination mechanisms; data control remains at the owners.

2.4.1. Tools to support data and organisation governance

As indicated, in contrast to the tools available for business modelling (which provide a structured approach for making design decisions on business models), governance literature lacks explicit tools and methods to support design decision making. Nonetheless, some tools have been identified that provide partial support towards our objective or can be used as a basis for designing a method to do so. In the following, we provide a brief descriptions of the identified tools.

2.4.1.1. Use Case Blueprint for data governance

The structured process proposed by the Data Sharing Coalition assists users in defining use cases (e.g. coherent set of actions and steps leading to a specified value proposition) for data sharing (Data Sharing Coalition, 2021). This use case blueprint challenges users when defining use cases for data sharing on aspects such as the value of data sharing, the prerequisites needed to facilitate data sharing (such as trust or interoperability) as well as the scalability and scope of the respective use case. Through this process, use cases are refined and detailed for data sharing and

can help generate commitment for organizations to pursue data sharing initiatives (based on its associated use cases). It is typically valuable in early phases of data sharing / data space development.

Figure 20 presents an overview of the process that is followed. In green field scenarios (i.e., in the case of a new technology or application for which no use cases have yet been defined), the process starts from step 1, focused on the generation of the use case, identifying why data sharing is relevant or what opportunities can be addressed. This results in a set of use cases for data sharing. As per step 2, these use cases should be scoped in terms of their timelines: when will the use cases be valuable or relevant? What timeline should be considered? As per step 3, the value of the use case consequently is assessed: what can be done with the use case, but also what is needed to realize the use case. Is the value worth the effort?

Figure 20: Use case blueprint - process (Data Sharing Coalition, 2021)

Step 4 delves into the complexity of the use case and what is needed for the use case to be operationalized. This step is important as it also specifies what is needed to facilitate trust and interoperability, for example on what governance structure is selected to facilitate the use case.

Step 5 concludes the use case definition process – in this step, concrete actions are defined for realizing the use case.

Each step is accompanied by templates to be filled in that help in further specifying and concretizing the use cases at hand, as well as best practices or inspirational cases. An example template for Step 3 (understanding the potential of the use case) is illustrated in Figure 21. Per use case, questions are posed and can be filled in by the respective stakeholders.

Use case name: <input type="text"/>		Examples in appendix >>	
What is the potential value for the Entitled party?		<input type="text"/>	
For the Entitled party, does the potential value outweigh the perceived risk associated with sharing data?		Yes / No	

Legend:

High = 2

Low = 1

None = -

Questions to answer to assess potential value for Data service provider(s), Data service consumer(s) and Enabling party/ies		Data service provider(s)	Data service consumer(s)	Enabling party/ies
Potential revenue increase	Is there potential for extra revenue from new or improved products or services?			
	Is there potential for extra revenue from improved customer relation?			
	Is there potential for extra revenue from transaction fees from revealing data?			
	Is there potential for extra revenue from other sources?			
Potential cost reduction	Is there potential for cost reduction due to improved internal efficiency?			
	Is there potential for cost reduction due to improved risk management?			
	Is there potential for cost reduction from other sources?			
Other	Contribution to strategic objectives, part of obligations or ethical branding			
Total per role				
Potential societal impact	What is the potential societal impact? This includes many topics, examples are improving sustainability, improving health, reducing poverty, increasing equality or contributing to a more circular economy		-	

Figure 21: Template used to support use case definition for data sharing (Data Sharing Coalition, 2021)

In addition to the blueprint, the data sharing coalition also proposes a three-stage approach that can help decision makers on further defining their use cases for data sharing. This three-stage approach is illustrated in Figure 22. One can see that the approach incorporates both aspects from organizational governance (roles, functions and responsibilities) as well as aspects from data governance (data model, legal aspect) to help in refining and enabling data sharing use cases. This is no different for data space development in which related questions and decisions have to be made. An example outcome of this use case definition approach is presented in Appendix B of this deliverable.

[Specification of scope, functionalities and enablers of data sharing use case]

Introduction

When designing your use case, a clear reason for why you want to achieve it and its scope is essential. Ensure that all involved stakeholders have a shared understanding of the use case ambition, the context, and future outlook of the use case. This creates a focus and a clear direction for the process of designing the use case.

In this stage, you will make design choices on three topics:

1. A clear ambition for the use case, external factors to consider, and relevant stakeholders with "Context and Goal"
2. Principles that should guide further decision-making with "Guiding Principles"
3. An outline of the data transaction(s) that are required in order to realise your intended use case goal through "Functional Scoping"

Relevant Topics

<p>Business</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Context and Goal (p. 6) Guiding Principles (p. 7) 	<p>Functional</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Functional Scoping (p. 8) 	<p>Operational</p> <p>N/A</p>
<p>Legal</p> <p>N/A</p>	<p>Technical</p> <p>N/A</p>	

[Per stage, important topics to consider. In step 1 (ambition), the relevant topics are the context and goal, scope and guiding principles. Note that these per step]

<p>Description</p> <p>Determine the goals of your use case (e.g. increase efficiency in your supply chain or resolving a shared challenge) and the external factors which could have an influence (e.g. regulation, changes in the market, etc.).</p> <p>Ensure you understand the complete ecosystem that your use case is part of such that you have an understanding of the external dependencies and the actors (including competitors) which may have an impact on the use case.</p> <p>By clearly defining the goal and context of the use case in the early stages of your design, you ensure a clear direction and scope for the further development of the use case.</p>	<p>Dependencies</p> <p>No dependencies on other topics</p>
<p>Considerations for scalability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Consider the future potential of the use case and how it could scale-up (e.g. additional functionality or actors involved). Take this long-term vision into account in the use case design. This will ensure no unnecessary barriers are raised which could block future developments 	<p>Questions</p> <p>Which problem(s) do you want to solve?</p> <p>What value do you aim to provide, and for whom?</p> <p>What external dependencies does your use case have?</p> <p>Other agreements on context and goal:</p>

[Detailed questions and description per topic to consider for use case definition].

Figure 22: Design decisions for use case definition (Data Sharing Coalition, 2021)

2.4.1.2. Templates for agreements to formalize governance

To guide decision making on the data governance, the agreement templates proposed in *Rulebook for fair data economy* (Pitkänen & Luoma-Kyyny, 2022) can be used. These templates address governance aspects such as *legal questions, description of the data network, code of conduct, terms and conditions, constitutive agreement, accession agreement, governance model and dataset terms of use* and are 'fillable' such that decision makers can readily use these templates to service their data governance decision making. An example of this template can be seen in Figure 23: the template includes categories to be answered by decisions makers as well as indicates how design decisions made can influence other data governance aspects.

Accordingly, data governance definition can be supported, structured and communicated.

Figure 23: Example template to support data governance decisions (Pitkänen & Luoma-Kyyny, 2022)

2.4.1.3. Data ecosystem canvas

SITRA proposes the Data Ecosystem Canvas (using the structure alike the Business Model Canvas) to support the generation of a high-level understanding of the business model for a given ecosystem. This can shed light on what the boundaries of the ecosystem or data space are, what its purpose is, what stakeholders should be involved, how and what data is exchanged, what services are needed, and importantly how the ecosystem is governed. On a high-level perspective, this tool therefore enables users to combine business thinking with clear governance modes, and can help in deciding on what generic governance structure should be selected. It generally serves to generate an early understanding of what value propositions

can be enabled by means of the data space and what governance modes can accommodate this. The Data Ecosystem Canvas is presented in Figure 24.

Figure 24: Data Ecosystem Canvas (from (Pitkänen & Luoma-Kyyny, 2022))

3. Synthesis of governance literature

Section 2.3 and 2.4 clearly demonstrate that governance of data spaces involves many different aspects. Different sources introduce similar and additional elements or characteristics for governance. Therefore, an attempt was made to synthesize the literature by clustering these elements to arrive at a conceptual model for defining data space governance.

3.1. Method for synthetization of the governance literature

The following approach was adopted to cluster the literature on governance.

The first step is to gather relevant scientific and grey literature related to governance, data governance and alliance governance. From these sources we elicited the key concepts, e.g., by inspecting the models, headers and lists. Next, we deployed an iterative approach to build categories, based on the Continuous Comparison Method (CCM) (Lincoln & Guba, 1985). This implies that concepts can be joined to an existing (emergent) category, or can form a new category. The procedure ends pragmatically when no new concepts or categories emerge, or when all literature is processed. The CCM approach can be illustrated by means of Figure 25.

Figure 25: Visualisation of the CCM approach for synthesizing literature

The following section provides the main result of the clustering. In the subsequent sections different categories are explained.

3.2. Conceptual governance model

Based on our synthesis of the governance literature, the conceptual governance model as illustrated in Figure 26 has been developed. This model serves as an initial starting point for data space governance and serves as the basis for the approach on support governance decision making. It will be validated as part of application for the SILLs, on the basis of which this governance model will be iteratively improved over time based on feedback collected.

Figure 26: 1st order governance categories

Below, we briefly describe each cluster or category of elements included for data space governance.

Position

Data sharing can be characterized along a long list of dimensions, e.g., mode of coordination (marketplace, hierarchy, alliance), its foundation (sharing pool, cooperative, public data trust), centralization (centralized, decentralized, federated), formalization.

Relevant questions are:

- What is the mode of governance? A marketplace, a hierarchy, a bazaar or an alliance/network.
- What is the organizational scope? Intra-organizational, inter-organisational, supra-organisational
- What is the control principle? Data platform (open), marketplace (transaction), sovereignty
- Where do the controls lie? Centralized (horizontal, vertical), decentralized (directed, collaborative, acknowledged, virtual), federated
- Where does the ownership of the data lies? Individual, organizational, shared
- What is the economic model? Data sharing pool, data cooperative, public data trust, personal data sovereignty, unilateral data sharing, data marketplace, data exchange, data ecosystem
- What is the legal form? Joint venture, foundation, union, cooperative, association, network
- What is the type of interdependence? Pooled, reciprocal
- What is the technical foundation? Infrastructure, data formats?

Purpose, principles and objectives

There are different types of objectives for engaging in a data-sharing initiative. These can be very high level, such as having access to (stakeholder) resources, or to accumulate (negotiation) power, or more data specific, such as achieving interoperability. High-level objectives are to combine, coordinate and manage collective (data or digital) resources. More general objectives include to manage risks and ensure continuity, to protect members or to maximize the value of data. More specific objectives relate to ambitions to achieve network effects (without being one platform) and to federate and achieve cross-domain interoperability. There are also objectives to avoid situations, like advertisement based business models, lock-ins.

The data-sharing initiative can adopt different principles and build its reason for existence also on compliance to applicable (and emerging) laws. There are principles for data, organizations and for innovation: (i) principles related to data are e.g., sovereignty, openness, security-by-design, privacy-by-design, (semantic) interoperability, trustworthiness; (ii) principles related to organisational aspects include openness, certain values, transparency, accountability and economic value; (iii) principles related to innovation and development include reuse of knowledge, avoidance of lock-ins, use of open source and open solutions, sustainability (amongst others).

Scope

A data-sharing initiative can express its scope in different ways, e.g., data, domain, organizations, resources, lifecycles. The purpose of this aspect is to propose several relevant dimensions to help initiatives define their scope.

Legal form

Data-sharing initiatives take on different legal forms (joint venture, foundation, union, cooperative, association, network).

Organisation, roles and decision-making

The organization and governance of an initiative can have various groups and bodies. Furthermore, an initiative will probably also have to interact with (several) overarching forms of governance, e.g. IDSA, national bodies, sectoral bodies (e.g., agricultural data space, green deal data space). Decision making and decision rights are key aspects of governance and should be defined here.

In the context of data-sharing, several organizations have described different roles that organizations can take on in the context of creating and capturing value with

data and also in context of data spaces (e.g. IDSA, SITRA, Data sharing Coalition, Gaia-X).

It is important to express roles and their associated functions and responsibilities that have a meaning for the technological system, the value network and legally.

It is important to distinguish roles that are related to the creation of value using data (i.e., data providers and users) and roles that enable the functioning of the data space (e.g., marketplace operator or identity service providers). There are also governance roles (e.g., certification body), which can overlap. In general data spaces are in the digital realm, so general software and service providers, like app providers, storage, consultancy providers will also find business in this context.

Furthermore some initiatives may already have adopted certain terminology.

Monitoring and change

An initiative cannot achieve its objectives right away and it may need to adapt to changes in the environment or preferences of the collective.

Life cycle

An initiative evolves through different life cycle stages.

Culture

Data-sharing can be introduced in very varying contexts, e.g., geographically, industrial domains, technically and organizationally. Understanding and addressing cross-organisational differences is key to effective governance.

Communication

Data-sharing initiatives are often aimed at growing and adoption of a wider ecosystem. As such, a (collective) marketing and communication strategy is an indispensable aspect for the organization to consider.

Risks

One of the key objectives of a governance approach is to manage (collective) risks. This requires active risk monitoring and management measures.

Services and resources

The initiative can organize different services and access to resources. These include core DATA SPACE services, such as Identity Services or Broker Services, but also support with compliance, or legal support, certification and admission services,

development of a supportive agenda, service level agreements and policies, data and data-processing services, security, communication and educations and more innovation services that are generally provided by digital innovation hubs (DIH), e.g., awareness creation, for innovation oriented services, like test beds or acceleration support.

Policies, standards, processes, procedures

An initiative needs to specify its strategic, tactical and operational processes and policies and specify which standards it wishes to adopt.

Governance can be achieved through several mechanisms, often combining mechanisms to do so. There are structural mechanisms, i.e., how the organisation is set up with roles and responsibilities and the structure of the initiative in general (e.g. marketplace or bazaar). There are also procedural mechanisms that define how things are done, e.g. how compliance or performance is monitored. Additionally, there are relational mechanisms that include aspects like communication and training and informal coordination. Ultimately, the chosen legal form (e.g. joint venture, cooperative, union) also affects specific roles and responsibilities.

Agreements

There are various ways of establishing parts of the desired behaviour, e.g., incentives, licenses, preconditions etc.

Tools and templates

In order to specify the governance model, several tools and templates are available. Tools and templates have been addressed in 2.4.1.

4. Methodology

To develop the proposed approach and to satisfy our research objective, we have followed a design science research (DSR) methodology (Hevner et al., 2004). Accordingly, we iteratively design the approach building upon literature on business modelling and governance to support data space development. To structure this design process, we have adopted the operationalized steps proposed by Peffers et al. (2007), namely:

1. Identify and motivate problem
2. Define objectives of a solution
3. Design and development
4. Demonstration and evaluation
5. Communication

The artifact we propose can be considered as a guiding approach to support design decision making on the governance structure and business models for data space development. . This approach is to be validated as part of Task 2.4 (occurring at a later point in time): the approach is to be used by SILLs to support data space development: through application of the approach, we generate insights on the strengths, weaknesses and merits of the approach as well as its usability. Based on feedback collected at (users for) the SILLs, we intend to further improve the approach.

4.1. Identify and motivate the problem

To identify and motivate our problem, we have conducted a literature review on the concepts of data spaces, (digital) business models and governance models. Through our literature review (see Chapter 2), we have clarified important elements and aspects to business modelling and governance models. We have also identified important tools that are used in the context of both concepts. However, as opposed to the technical dimension of data spaces, we see that both business and governance models have received limited attention in the context of data space development. Accordingly, there is a lack of support in terms of design decision making on these concepts to support the development of new data space initiatives. Business models enable decision makers and stakeholders to clarify how new technologies contribute to value creation or enable new solutions, thus motivating the development and operation of new data spaces. In addition, as data spaces enable the exchange of data with virtually all stakeholders connected to the initiative, this calls for rules and protocols on how data is shared, how the data space is coordinated and governed, and how decision making rights are distributed. It is evident that these concepts are highly interrelated: design decisions for governance influence what value propositions can be offered. Striving for certain business models in the other hand calls for explicit consideration of governance models and

mechanisms. More so, such considerations should be flexible or 'open' in nature to support scaling of the data space over time. To support data space development, guidance on design decisions for these concepts is needed. Accordingly, we address the research objective:

"What approach can be defined to support the design of the governance and business models for the development of data spaces to support FLW reduction?"

4.2. Define objectives of a solution

Based on the literature search and the highlighted practical and theoretical gap identified, we define the following artefact objectives:

Obj₁: The proposed artefact should guide decision makers in articulating the value propositions for data space business models, as well as in application of specific business models that can be created through a data space. Therefore, a consortium that is pursuing the development of a data space should be able to use the approach as a mean to understand what value propositions can be connected to / enabled by means of the data space.

Obj₂: The proposed artefact should help decision makers in defining and concretizing governance structures to support data sharing for data spaces, providing hand-holds to decision makers on what decisions should be made during the development of the data space.

Obj₃: As a result of objective 1 and 2, the proposed artefact should support the development and roll-out of data spaces in practice. This includes opportunities for scaling.

4.3. Design and development of the approach

We have iteratively designed our approach through a series of brainstorming workshops, in which we built upon the literature findings identified through step 2 as well as leveraging the experience of our research team. This involved integrating the tools and methods identified as part of the literature review into a workable approach. Additionally, it involved defining a conceptual background to which these tools and methods could be mapped as part of the approach. For these brainstorming workshops, 4 researchers were involved, each with significant experience on business modelling, governance mechanisms, and data ecosystems and data spaces. The resulting intermediate version (alpha version) of this approach was validated with SILL stakeholders as part of an interactive workshop to understand the initial validity, usefulness and ease-of-use of the approach. Feedback collected through this SILL-focused workshop was used to further improve on the approach (beta version). This beta version will be used to support real-life pilots in the context of food waste as part of task 2.4.

4.4. Demonstration, use and evaluation of the approach

As explained, to understand the initial validity, usefulness and ease-of-use of the approach, we orchestrated an interactive evaluation workshop with SILL stakeholders. In this workshop, the alpha version of the approach was presented and illustrated to SILL stakeholders. Stakeholders were encouraged to ask questions on aspects of the approach as well as its use in practice. At the end of the workshop, stakeholders were asked to fill in a short questionnaire on the validity, usefulness, and ease-of-use of the approach. The questionnaire was built upon the *Technology Acceptance Model (TAM-Model)* to operationalize the evaluation criteria through a series of questions (Venkatesh et al., 2003). Feedback generated through this questionnaire was used to further refine the method (beta version).

As explained, the validation and evaluation of beta version of the approach will be conducted through the task 2.4. In this task, we expect to support the application of the approach in several ways depending on the characteristics of the respective SILLs: for example, some SILLs may already be concrete or mature (in terms of potential business models or data space use cases) or may possess ample business modelling to accommodate the use of the approach. In such cases, we will support the application of the approach through a consultant or facilitator role, providing feedback where needed on whether steps have been applied correctly. Contrastingly, some of the SILLs may call for more hands-on support for the application of the approach, as the potential uses of the data space are still unclear or the business acumen needed to support business modelling activities is limited. We expect that for each SILL a tailor-made approach is drafted to help the application of the approach.

4.5. Communication

The final step of the DSR approach entails the communication of our results. We intend to use internal channels for the project to communicate our approach to the SILLs as well as to interested partners and stakeholders. Moreover, we intend to publish (part of the) results of our study in academic outlets such as IS and business modelling related conferences and journals.

5. Design approaches for business models and governance

In this chapter, we operationalize three design approaches for the development of business models and governance. Specifically, we elaborate how the approach is used in action as well as what tools can be considered to support its execution.

5.1. Overarching design approach

Business models and governance models in the context of data-driven applications and data sharing involve multiple choices that have to be made in coherence by multiple organisations: think of the data sources, access conditions, algorithms, interfaces, onboarding rules, service levels. It is too complex for a single person to make the correct choices for all options available and to expect that this will yield the desired outcomes and impacts, supported by all organizations involved. To deal with this, we approach both the business modelling and governance modelling as a design. This implies that we use or develop templates as models for the choices at hand. Next, based on the understanding and interpretation of the relevant contexts and objectives, such templates are filled in a collaborative way by multiple stakeholders. This results in a complete draft design that is evaluated against chosen criteria. This will lead to identification of improvement suggestions or critical assumptions. These should be tested by means of explorative or validation experiments. Results of the experiment are incorporated in the overarching design, until evaluation yields satisfactory results to commit to implementation.

Designing the appropriate governance structure as well as the exploration, design and evaluation of business models for data spaces can significantly benefit from tool support. In Figure 27, we present an overview of the three design approaches we propose, and their targeted outputs.

Figure 27: Overview of design approaches

The first approach is an approach for designing the collaborative business model for the data-driven applications that are in focus of the SILLs. The output, a specification of a collaborative business model, provides a good overview of how organizations related to the data-driven application together create and capture value. This can be

taken forward by the individual organizations in their individual decision making processes, e.g. by further detailing the forthcoming business cases or investment plans. Here, one can refer to the H2020 Ploutos approach (Berkers et al., 2022), as presented in Section 2.2.4.1.1.

The second approach is a very similar approach. This however focuses on the specification of the collaborative business model for the data space that supports the data-sharing necessary for the data-driven applications in the SILLs and similar applications and extensions. This approach will take the reference roles that are related to data sharing, following the international data spaces approach as a starting point. It will project these roles onto the organizations that partake in the data-sharing, typically organizations involved in the data-driven application. As a starting point, the reference business model design for data spaces (Figure 11) can be used. The development and evaluation of such collaborative business model follows similar steps as the previous approach, mapping concrete stakeholders to the high-level roles identified.

The third approach is focused on the design of the governance of the data space that is needed to ensure the availability of the data for data-driven application (of the SILL). The 3rd approach is most elaborated upon in this deliverable (given its newness) and builds forward on a few existing toolsets of the Data Sharing Coalition and of SITRA. We refer to Section 2.4.1 for a detailed discussion on these tools.

5.1.1. Design approaches in a SILL/application development context

Figure 28 presents an overview of the approach and the design insights (in terms of governance and business models) that should be collected and validated to support the development of data spaces. As indicated, ideally these layers are considered jointly and are simultaneously developed over time. In other words, we suggest the design approaches to be executed in parallel. This conceptual background will be further detailed as part of Chapter 6.

Figure 28: Approach to support business decision making for DATA SPACE development

In the subsequent sections of this chapter, we detail each of these approaches by proposing a sequence of “design workshops” in which a specific task is executed and a corresponding tool is suggested.

5.2. Design approach for SILL / Data Driven Business Model (1)

This section builds on the Collaborative Business Model approach as described in section 2.2.4.1.1.

Figure 29: Design approach for collaborative business model for data-driven applications of the SILL

The development of *application-specific* business models can benefit from the use of best practices or reference business models catered to a specific domain. In the context of ZeroW, reference business models that describe solutions (aimed at FLW) and generic stakeholder roles needed to support such solutions can help in ideating application-specific business models. For example, the cases described in Section 2.2.3 or the reference model proposed in Section 2.2.4.1.2 can serve as inspiration for the ideation of FLW business models enabled by the to-be developed data space. For these cases, generic roles can be identified (such as service providers, food producers or retailers) that can be mapped to the concrete stakeholders / users present for the to-be developed data-driven application. This is particularly relevant in early phases of development, as in these phases it is important to understand what value propositions should be enabled by means of a new data space (warranting its existence). Nevertheless, the reference FLW business models can also be used as part of scaling the data-driven applications and consequently the space (i.e. what additional business models can potentially be enabled by means of the data space, or what adaptations to the data space are needed to do so).

To develop these collaborative business models, we propose the workshop approach as developed in H2020 project Ploutos (see Berkers et al. (2022) for more detail on this approach). This is a series of workshops in which actors from the SILL work on analysis and design tasks. These workshops are facilitated by a business modelling expert and typically take around 2 hours. Below, we briefly summarize the different tasks and workshops. It should be noted that the order and contents of these workshops can be tailored to the specific needs of the SILL. Example business models generated through this approach are presented in the Appendix A of this deliverable. An overview of the approach is illustrated in Figure 29.

1. Onboarding

As developing business models with a group of different people in context of a project requires a certain understanding, commitment and trust of the participants,

the first step to take is to get acquainted and ensure safety of participants to share thoughts and observations.

2. Customer journey and DAMIAN tool mapping

To be able to create value for a customer it is important to understand the process he or she is in (e.g., food production), to understand information needs and other actors involved, a so-called customer journey can be mapped.

A second task executed is to identify the technologies and systems needed to generate, process and deliver data or services. Here, the DAMIAN tool is used to do so (Berkers et al., 2014).

3. Business model radar

The third workshop is devoted to populating the business model design, as described in the introduction of this section. In this workshop, the Service-Dominant Business Model Radar will be used to do so (Turetken et al., 2019). Note that this is only a first draft of the business model. In the next steps it will iteratively be defined.

4. Theory of change

In the context of this (and other) projects, business models are not only a view on exploitation of innovations, but also a means to achieve societal value, i.e., sustainability. Put differently, the purpose of the collaborative business model is to describe and capture the value creation among participating actors. It is however expected that such business model would also lead to reduction of FLW. This implies that there will be assumptions on the scale of application and behaviours of humans and organizations related to this application. By means of detailing the theory of change (the causal network of inputs, activities, outputs, outcomes and impacts), assumptions and prerequisites can be identified. This helps to create a shared view, and identify risks and take appropriate measures.

5. Evaluation

The purpose of this task is to evaluate the business model, identify suggestions for improvement and prepare for decision making. Typically the dimensions of desirability, viability and feasibility can be considered, but alternative dimensions, such as sustainability and robustness can also be considered – this depends on the motives and objectives of the stakeholders involved.

6. Experimentation

The last task is to move towards implementation of the business model. Typically details, e.g., with regards to the business case or actor acceptance, need to be specified or more detailed choices need to be made. This may be done by conducting experiments. Also, it involves defining concrete next steps for business model realization. It is expected that organizations can take the collaborative business model design into their organizations' decision making processes for further commitment.

5.3. Design approach for Data Space roles Business Model (2)

This section builds on the Collaborative Business Model approach as described in section 2.2.4.1.1 and the data space reference business model as depicted in Figure 11.

The purpose of this design approach is to design a collaborative business model for the parties that together intend to ensure that there is a data space available for the SILL and its data-driven applications, and that the effort and costs associated with this can be covered by income. The basis for the approach is similar to the previous section.

Figure 30: Design approach for the collaborative business model of roles of a data space

There are however two main differences that deserve highlighting here. The first is that the core value proposition is not a data-driven OFLW service, but a data space enabled virtual data-sharing facility. The second is that several aspects related to such business model are more or less known. These are: the customer journey and the technological architecture are given and the 'theory of change' as well. As said, in the context of data-sharing, several organizations have described different roles that organizations can take on in the context of creating and capturing value with data and also in the context of data spaces (e.g. IDSA, SITRA, Data Space Coalition, Gaia-X). Each set of roles has slightly different names and interpretations. A useful (but not authoritative) overview of roles is given in Section 2.1.1.2. In light of the previous business modelling approach, it is also possible to design the collaborative business model of a data space by means of the business model radar and by identifying which real-world actors play those roles. An overview of the design approach for data space business models is illustrated in Figure 30.

1. Onboarding

Same as for the previous section (5.2).

2. Customer journey and DAMIAN tool

This step is not applicable for this design approach, as the customer processes and the technological set up for data spaces generally is similar across applications. Therefore it has been greyed out in the figure above. For guidance on data space design from a technical perspective, we refer to D2.1 (Cornelisse, 2022).

3. Data space roles business model radar

The actors related to the SILL are mapped to the existing overviews of roles and vice versa, to see which roles are vacant and which have multiple candidates and the business model is further detailed. As explained, the reference business model for data spaces can be used as a starting point here. For ease of reading, the reference business model for data space business model design is illustrated below (see Figure 31).

Figure 31: Reference business model for data space business model design

4. Theory of Change

This step is not applicable for this design approach: the logic towards impact is defined by the application-specific business models and less relevant to be considered here separately.

5. Evaluation

Same as for previous section (5.2).

6. Experimentation

Same as for previous section (5.2).

5.4. Design approach for Data Space governance (3)

This section builds on the governance tools presented in section 2.4.1.

The third design is aimed at establishing the complete governance for a data space that ensures the data availability for a SILL and its data-driven applications. In Figure 32 an overview of the different proposed steps is given. As compared to the previous sections this approach is very elaborate as a result of the wide range of topics that are associated with data and organisational governance. As a consequence the steps of specification and formalization are expected to require multiple workshops.

Figure 32: Design approach for Data Space governance

In contrast to the approaches proposed for business modelling, this approach as presented is not validated in practice. Yet, it is built upon two test and tried methods:

- The Use Case Blueprint approach by the Data Sharing Coalition (see section 2.4.1.1)
- The agreement templates collected in SITRA's Rulebook for a fair data economy (see section 2.4.1.2)

Furthermore, by contrasting the contents of these methods with the extant literature on governance, we identified several aspects that were barely or not well covered in the existing approaches. This still needs further elaboration, but the "deep-dive" step is meant to check these with the stakeholders.

Below, we briefly describe the different steps presented.

1. Onboarding

Similar purpose as above. Since both the collaborative business model for the data space as well as this governance design are focused on choices for the data space, these onboarding activities could be combined (also depending on the facilitating and the participating team).

2. Scan

The first content based step in the governance design process is a scan that covers a series of topics that are closely related to the governance. This serves as a starting point in the process and reveals which topics are already thought of and which not. It will thus inform the remainder of the process. To do so, we use the Data Ecosystem Canvas as it represents a comprehensive yet easy to use first step for understanding what purpose or goal is achieved by means of the data space. This existing tool is

part of the Rulebook (see section 2.4.1.3). For ease of reading, the Data Ecosystem Canvas is presented below (see Figure 33).

Note that this scan includes ‘governance’ (bottom-right) as a topic. This may appear somewhat counter-intuitive, as that is what needs to be designed. Aspects like, e.g., services and infrastructure, are key to understand, as ensuring services and infrastructure should be supported by the governance design.

Data Ecosystem Canvas		
Purpose and core needs What is the key purpose / problem why the ecosystem exists? What are the (initial) key use cases? What is the context of the data ecosystem? How is value generated and distributed in the data ecosystem?		Issues and questions What issues and questions are raised regarding the case?
Key stakeholder and their roles Who are the key stakeholders, i.e. Data providers and data consumers and their roles?		Services and infrastructure What value adding services are needed in the ecosystem? What infrastructure is required?
Ecosystem scope, rules and business models What is in- and out of scope? What are the ground principles of the ecosystem? What is the driving business logic and model?	Data streams and value transfer (give-gets) What data streams are covered by the ecosystem? What value is generated and transferred between entities (give)? How value is compensated (get)?	Governance and KPIs Who/how is the ecosystem created? How is the ecosystem governed and how its is monitored? What is the change mechanism for the ecosystem?

Figure 33: Data Ecosystem Canvas as a Scan for the design of the governance

3. Deep-dive

As illustrated in Chapter 2 and synthesized as per Chapter 3, the concept of governance is multi-faceted. Through the synthesis of how current work already deals with governance, we have built a broad overview of relevant factors and aspects (for ease of reading, we reintroduce the conceptual model in Figure 34). We use this overview to identify to what extent the existing approaches are complete. For example, looking at the scan of the previous section. There is a topic ‘purpose and core needs’. Addressing the related questions may also yield in questions like: ‘What are typical purposes and examples of purpose definitions for data sharing initiatives?’. The “deep-dive” session is meant to introduce the governance topics that require background. This session is needed to tailor the subsequent sessions, by inspecting with the initiative which topics need further attention.

The material for such deep-dive is not yet available. It will be based on the work reported in Chapter 3.

Figure 34: Conceptual map of governance related topics

4. Specification

The next step is to detail, or specify, all elements of the governance. At first this can be done in a draft or explorative mode, taking into account the aspects introduced in the deep-dive. The Use Case Blueprint method (see section 2.4.1.1) is used to capture the initiative's inputs on the various aspects. For ease of reading, we elaborate how the use case blueprinting is used for the approach.

Use Case Blueprint

The Use Case Blueprint approach consists of a great number of templates (11), divided over three sections. In this section we list the different topics covered in the Use Case Blueprint and link these to the concepts introduced in the conceptual governance model of Chapter 2. To answer the questions on the templates, it is important for the users (and facilitators) to understand the elements of the conceptual model. This is why these need to be described and presented in a way to be useful in context of design workshops. In Section 5.4.1.1 we detail what development is required for each of the elements of the governance model. *This development is however not part of this deliverable.*

1: Scope and Ambition

- Context & Goal – see Section 3.2 *Purpose, principles and objectives* and *Position*
- Guiding Principles – see Section 3.2 *Purpose, principles and objectives*
- Functional Scoping – see Section 3.2 *Scope*

2: Functionalities

- Roles and Responsibilities – see 3.2 *Organisation, roles and decision-making*

- Functional Components – see 3.2 *Services and resources*
- Interaction Model – see 3.2 *Organisation, roles and decision-making*

3: Enablers

- Business topics (fee structures, branding) – see Section 5.2 and 5.3, collaborative business modelling.
- Legal topics (rules and regulations, contracts, governance structure) – see 3.2 *Agreements and Policies, standards, processes and procedures* and *Organisation, roles and decision-making*
- Functional topics (user experience, privacy features) – See 3.2 *Services and resources*
- Technical (technical specification, information security) – See 3.2 *Services and resources*
- Operational topics (information management, operational governance, risk management) – See 3.2 *Services and resources* and *Policies, standards, processes, procedures* and *Organisation, roles and decision-making* and *Risks*

5. Evaluation

Similar as above (5.2).

6. Formalization

To guide decision making on the data governance structure, the templates proposed in *Rulebook for fair data economy* (Pitkänen & Luoma-Kyyny, 2022) can be used (2.4.1.2). These templates formalize governance aspects such as *legal questions, description of the data network, code of conduct, terms and conditions, constitutive agreement, accession agreement, governance model* and *dataset terms of use* and are 'fillable' such that decision makers can readily use these templates to service their data governance decision making. An example of this template can be seen in Figure 23. The template includes categories to be answered by decisions makers as well as indicates how design decisions made can influence other data governance aspects. Accordingly, data governance definition can be supported.

The Rulebook provides the following templates for specification. The choices and considerations from the previous steps can be formalized in these.

1. A template for the Dataset Terms of Use – reflects *Principles and Standards* (Section 3.2)
2. A template for the Accession Agreement – reflects *Principles and Organisation, Roles and Decision-making* (Section 3.2)
3. A template for the Constitutive Agreement – reflects *Purpose, Principles and Objectives* (Section 3.2)

4. The General Terms and Conditions (to be used as-is) – reflects *Principles* (Section 3.2)
5. A template for a Code of Conduct – reflects *Principles* (Section 3.2)
6. A template for a Description of the Data Network – reflects *Position* (Section 3.2)
7. A template for establishing the answers to the contractual framework's key Legal Questions
8. A template for the Governance Model – reflects *Organisation, roles and decision-making* and *Policies, standards, procedures and processes* (see Section 3.2).

Following the formalization, the agreements can be signed and consequently will be in effect. To support this formalization workshop, the set of requirements proposed in D2.1 (Cornelisse, 2022) can be used (see Appendix C): these requirements capture the high-level needs for data space governance that should be formalized as part of this governance approach. For ease of use, we have mapped these requirements to the SITRA templates (Pitkänen & Luoma-Kyyny, 2022) which can be used to provide input towards concretizing these requirements. Accordingly, using Appendix C, users can quickly refer to the correct templates proposed in case certain requirements have not been (fully) addressed.

5.4.1.1. Governance aspects requiring additional development for operationalisation

We believe that the design approach can benefit if the following list of topics is further detailed and explained (e.g. presentations, brief summaries and overviews), and potentially turned into tooling. We see this as an add-on to the existing tooling. *The detailing of these is not in the scope of this deliverable.*

Position

Develop an overview with different dimensions and a tool to position the initiative under consideration, potentially with some additional well-known examples. The purpose of this aspect is to support organizations in understanding the different choices and clearly positioning the initiative.

Purpose, principles and objectives

Develop an overview of different principles and different objective types (and examples). The purpose of this aspect is to provide organizations with broader background into possible principles and objectives for data-sharing initiatives.

Scope

Develop an overview of typical dimensions on which initiatives can be scoped, e.g., data, domain, organizations, resources, lifecycles. The purpose of this aspect is to propose several relevant dimensions to help initiatives define their scope.

Legal form

Develop an overview of legal forms, their identified roles and obligations. Add pros, cons and considerations. The purpose of this aspect is to introduce different legal options and understand their implications.

Organisation, roles and decision-making

Provide a reference organisational structure that can be stripped or phased. Develop a role model and typical rights and decisions. Develop a reference list of (external) governance bodies, e.g. IDSA, to link to. The purpose is to provide the organization with appropriate sets of roles to specify the different levels of governance. Additionally, the purpose of this aspect is to identify the potential governance bodies that should be addressed in the governance design.

Monitoring and change

Develop a reference overview of KPIs and monitoring templates and change use cases, change procedures and associated roles. The purpose of this aspect is to help the organization define monitoring and change procedures.

Life cycle

Develop a life cycle model and propose characteristics associated with each phase. The purpose of this aspect is to facilitate the phased development of the initiative.

Culture

Develop culture assessment tests. Understanding and addressing cross-organisational differences is key to effective governance.

Communication

Develop a reference marketing & communication strategic plan and role, as well as internal communication channels. The purpose of this aspect is ensure internal and external communication.

Risks

Develop an overview of typical risks and a basic risk management procedure. The purpose of this aspect is to consider risk management as part of the governance design.

Services and resources

Develop an overview of typical services and resources. The purpose of this aspect is to introduce a broad spectrum of services that an initiative can organize to meet its objectives.

Policies, standards, processes, procedures

Develop an overview of typical standards (for organisation and data) and reference processes. The purpose of this topic is to identify the different policies, standards and processes that need to be in place.

Agreements

Develop an overview and examples of governance mechanisms and agreements. The purpose of this aspect is to introduce a broader overview of governance mechanisms and instruments to consider in the governance design.

6. Conceptual background for proposed approach

In this section, we describe the conceptual background for our approach to support business decision making on governance and business models for data spaces. As indicated, we identify that 3 co-evolving layers should be considered to support the development of data spaces and for which design decisions should be made. These interrelated layers are:

- *Application-specific business models*, describing the application-specific business models that are enabled through a data space .
- *Data space business models*, describing the overall business model of stakeholders related to the data spaces.
- *Data space governance structure*, describing the governance structure selected to support interactions, collaborations and data sharing for the data space.

Each of these categories follows the data space development process and therefore poses questions or requirements which should be fulfilled to motivate continued development of the data space. In the following, we will detail for *data space business models*, *application-specific business models* and *data space governance structure* what tasks are to be executed per phase and how this contributes to realizing Go / No-Go decisions.

The business model layers (i.e. application-specific business models and data space business models) capture the *why* of developing a data space: what value can we enable for users of the data space, but also for stakeholders to the data space? What new value propositions can be established as a result of the data space? Are users and stakeholders better off through data space participation? These layers therefore make explicit what the purpose of the data space is and in what way it will contribute to reaching business value / achieving the objectives of the data space. The governance structure and technical architecture represent the *how* of developing a data space: what decisions regarding the architecture of the data space should be made to facilitate data sharing? What rules and policies are required to stimulate FAIR use of data and foster trust and collaboration between data space users? These layers therefore define how the data space will work. Logically, the *why* and *how* are interrelated: design decisions made regarding the *why* influence what technical architecture or governance structure is needed to accommodate this. Conversely, selecting a certain governance mode can influence what value can be created and therefore influence the 'why' of developing a data space: it may motivate or make organisations reluctant to participate as more or less value can be created.

Each of these layers pose design decisions that should be answered during the development phases of data spaces. Such phases can follow general development cycles for any new technology, initiative or solution: *exploration*, *piloting*, *operation and scaling*. In such a development cycle, design decisions between the exploration

and piloting phase, as well as between the operating and scaling phase, can be iterative in nature: data space development can move freely from exploration to piloting (and vice-versa), as well from operation to scaling. For example, for the former, evaluation and test outcomes may highlight that for the current governance structure selected, limited value can be created as part of the business models supported by the data space. Accordingly, decision makers can 'revert' back to the exploration phase to rethink what the most appropriate governance structure should be. For the latter, scaling the data space will lead to a 'new' status quo of operations (e.g. a data space with an increased amount or diversified set of users). From that point onwards, new scaling intentions can be pursued (moving towards the scaling phase). Therefore, both transitions between phases are characterized by 'soft' Go/No-Go decisions. However, a more strict transition occurs between the piloting phase and operation phase: once the piloting phase is completed, the data space is deployed in practice (meaning that activities such as exploration and piloting, at least for the current setup for the data space) do not take place. This is characterized by a hard Go/No-Go decision: commitment of stakeholders to proceed should be achieved.

We assume that each of the layers start from a more or less 'greenfield scenario' (i.e. no limitations are imposed by previous work in terms of business or technical development): therefore, each of the layers (business models, governance, technical architecture) will go through the development phases specified. Logically, in practice, decision makers may already have validated business models or have trialled initial configurations of the technical architecture or governance structure applicable. For example, in the case of SCSN, several pilot or trial-and-error instances of deployment have preceded the actual roll-out of the data space in practice, after which the data space has been scaled over time. In this moment, decision makers investigate what additional business models can be enabled through use of the data space to make participation worthwhile in the long run. This illustrates that in practice these layers do not always have to follow a similar pace in terms of proceeding through development cycles. Nonetheless, design decisions made for a certain layer can significantly influence other layers – a joint consideration of layers is therefore recommended.

In the following, we will detail for *data space business models, application-specific business models and data space governance structure* what tasks are to be executed per phase and how this contributes to realizing Go / No-Go decisions.

6.1. Application-specific business models

As explained, the application-specific business models describe the business models that are *enabled* by means of data sharing in the data space. For example, through data sharing for supply chain actors, new or enhanced value propositions can be

offered to supply chain customers. Such data sharing can be facilitated by (collaboration between) service providers active for the data space. A detailed view of how application-specific business models fit the data space development process is illustrated in Figure 35. In the following, we elaborate for each phase what activities should be undertaken and how these activities can be supported.

6.1.1. Exploration phase for application-specific business models

The exploration phase for application-specific business models focuses on understanding what application-specific business models can be enabled by service providers associated to the platform (which as explained are the customers or end-user for the data space business model). To do so, stakeholders should consider what *solutions* and *associated value propositions* can be offered by service providers to its own customers as a result of the data space. What purpose does the data space serve for service providers involved? What can they do differently for their customers through the data space? How does this translate into renewed or improved value propositions for their own customers or what novel solutions can be offered as a result? Is the data space currently under consideration actually valuable or useful to service providers? Should we pursue this data space, can meaningful value propositions be associated to it?

Stakeholders should also investigate how such solutions may affect existing (supply chain) business models for these customers. What implications does the data space enabled solution have for current business models? Does it disrupt the structure of existing supply chains or can supply-chain wide effects be achieved as a result of the data space enabled solution(s)? In relation to this, stakeholders should judge what the initial viability of the new business models can be, by looking at how value is created and captured for these application-specific business models. For example, what revenue model is selected for providing the data space enabled solution and what benefits can (supply chain) stakeholders generate through (access to) the proposed solution. If the *initial viability* of the supported business models proves to be low (either because limited value can be created by stakeholders or because there is no strategic relevance for using the data space enabled solutions through service providers), this may indicate that in its current form data space development is not warranted (as service providers are not able to provide meaningful value propositions to *their* customers). Note that this does not necessarily have to depend on the amount of business models that can be supported, but rather on the degree to which the service provider can capture value through data space enabled business models (which requires a viable business scenario for supply chain stakeholders). In case this cannot be achieved, this calls for reconsideration of how the data space is structured or what potential solutions should or can be enabled through the data space.

Figure 35: Application specific business model (A-BM) development to support data space development

6.1.2. Piloting phase for application-specific business models

Analogously to the piloting phase for the data space business model, the piloting phase for application-specific business models should focus on evaluating the *viability, desirability, feasibility* and *robustness* of the application-specific business models. As explained, the pilot phase addresses the (test-bed) implementation and use of the proposed data space. Through the data space, connected service providers can then provide data space based solutions to their customers. As a consequence, it should become apparent to what extent the value propositions and business models ideated in the exploration phase can hold or whether technical or business challenges are faced. Accordingly, the *viability, feasibility* and *desirability* of the application-specific business models can be assessed. Does the introduction of the data space enabled solution by service providers enable supply chain stakeholders to create value? Is this value sufficient in light of potential costs or business model adaptations to be made? If not, does this call for potential business model redesign, or do we see that the viability or desirability for customers of service providers cannot be sufficiently addressed?

Similarly, stakeholders should investigate to what extent the business models are robust in nature: for example, what happens if supply chain stakeholders switch service providers which are not connected to the data space? What does this imply for the value that can be created? Again, data collected through testing of the data space can be used to complement this analysis.

The piloting phase should be concluded with insights on the *viability, feasibility, desirability* and *robustness* of the application-specific business models. It should be clear to service providers to what extent they can enable new or additional value to their customers, warranting participation for the data space. In turn, this motivates data space implementation in practice. This should be interpreted as a 'hard' Go/No-Go' decision.

6.1.3. Operation phase for application-specific business models

In the operation phase, the performance of the application-specific business models should be monitored to sustain the participation of service providers and to aid in potential technical or business difficulties that are faced post-launch. The viability of these business models should be continuously assessed to understand whether the business models enabled through data spaces have longevity warranted by service providers to participate for the data space. In case inviable business scenarios are obtained, the design of application-specific business models may have to be (incrementally) adapted to accommodate this (for example to alter the revenue model selected or to rethink part of the value capture logic for the business model design).

In addition to analysing current application-specific business models, stakeholders should also investigate how the value propositions of service providers to *their customers* can be extended or enriched. For example, in case new service providers participate for the data space (particularly those active in similar domains), new data space enabled solutions can potentially be established, which may warrant the exploration of additional business models. These can help in extending the value propositions service providers can offer to their customers. Therefore, in this phase, stakeholders should explore to opportunities for scaling in regards to the growing user base of service providers: what additional solutions can be established as a result of this? How can it impact or scale existing application-specific business models? As usual, this exploration should be accommodated through an initial assessment of the viability of the resulting scaled application-specific business models or the extended set of application specific business models.

6.1.4. Scaling phase for application-specific business models

Similar to the scaling phase for the overall data space business model, this phase should address the (continued) investigation of scaling opportunities for application-specific business models. Again, this may relate to scaling business models already under consideration or exploring what new potential application-specific business models can be taken into account. Note that the data space does not have to remain domain specific but can freely scale for many domains depending on whether this from an evaluation perspective can be justified. Accordingly, in terms of scaling application-specific business models, also cross-domain solutions may be considered (between service providers active in different domains).

6.2. Data space business models

The data space business model describes the stakeholders that collectively deploy the data space (such as brokers, clearing house service providers, governing bodies), how they collaborate and how they are able to create value for service and application providers and capture value in return. A detailed view of how data space business models fit the data space development process is illustrated in Figure 36. In the following sections, we elaborate for each phase what activities should be undertaken and how these activities can be supported.

6.2.1. Exploration phase for data space business models

In the exploration phase, the focus is on understanding the overall business model design appropriate for supporting the data space. As a first step, stakeholders should decide on the domain that is considered for the data space, as this influences the potential customers or users that should be considered for the data space. For example, positioning the data space for the food industry or automotive industry

has implications for what type of service providers (end-users of the data space) can be involved. Even though the data space could very well serve multiple domains (particularly if data exchange for different domains is highly similar), stakeholders should agree on what domains the data space will service. Consequently, the share of potential service providers that can be considered as 'end-users' can be determined. In analysing this share of potential service providers (the user base of the data space), it is important to understand how these service providers can enable new value propositions or different business models for *their* customers. Therefore, this activity for data space business models is strongly related to the exploration phase for application-specific business models.

In addition to understanding the potential end-users for the data space, data space stakeholders should also shed light on who should be involved to support the (operation and implementation of) the data space: what roles are required to facilitate the working of the data space and what concrete stakeholders can be mapped to these roles? Are these roles already present for our consortium / collaboration? Depending on the concrete stakeholders to be involved, one should also decide what collaboration form is selected: will the data space be the result of a joint venture or are other forms of collaboration considered? What are the drivers of each stakeholder and can this influence the appropriateness of governance structures? These decision shed light on how the data space business model design should be shaped and what this implies in a strategic sense for stakeholders involved (and whether this is acceptable or not). This activity has strong interrelationship with the governance structure selected for the data space, particularly in terms of how organisational governance is structured.

Figure 36: Data space business models to support data space development

Part of the exploration phase for data space business models also means investigating how value is created and captured by stakeholders involved. Depending on what governance structure is selected and the potential set of end-users, stakeholders should decide on how each stakeholder is able to capture value in return. On the basis of this, stakeholders can determine to what extent the data space business model design *initially* (i.e. conceptually) is viable: can a viable business scenario for data space stakeholders be obtained? What does each stakeholder roughly have to invest and what revenue (or other benefits) does it receive in return? Does this motivate continued exploration of the data space in a tested (piloted) environment? Depending on the outcome of this preliminary evaluation, the data space business model design may be adapted (different domain, different governance forms).

6.2.2. Piloting phase for data space business models

In the piloting phase, the conceptual data space business models defined for the exploration phase should be further concretized and evaluated based on initial (test) results. As a result of piloting the data space, it should become apparent to what extent the value proposition for service providers can actually be realized (as service providers as part of the pilot will use the data space). This should shed light on whether data space is actually *desirable* for end-users of the data space and thus provide insights on the potential users base that can be considered. It is important that the desirability of the data space for end-users is evaluated to support the data space business model.

Logically, the insights generated on the perceived value or desirability of the data space also influences the degree to which the data space business model is actually *viable*: it influences the amount of revenue that can be captured through the data space (dependent on the user base) and thus what value is captured by data space stakeholders involved. In addition to this, through piloting of the data space it also becomes increasingly apparent what the costs of data space implementation and operation will be. What does the viability of the data space imply for each stakeholder involved? What changes to the business model design can be made in case inviable business scenarios are obtained? Therefore, this phase should incorporate a quantified *business case* analysis of whether it makes sense to continue data space development.

In addition to the business perspective, it should also be evaluated to what extent the data space business model can be implemented: do current stakeholders have access to the necessary resources to operate and support the data space once rolled-out? If not, what changes to the business model design can be made to facilitate data space operation? Furthermore, stakeholders should also explore the robustness of the data space business model: to what extent is the data space

business model proofed against future trends or changes for the stakeholder network involved? What happens in case a stakeholder decides to drop out for data space operation? To what extent can this be mitigated as part of the data space business model?

The goal of the piloting phase is to agree on a finalized business model design and to evaluate the business model for the aforementioned criteria. Using these criteria (i.e. *desirability for end-users, viability for data space stakeholders, feasibility and robustness of data space business model*), stakeholders should determine whether it makes sense to pursue the data space business model and to generate commitment from each stakeholder involved. As mentioned, this is a hard Go / No-Go decision, as advancing to the next phase means that investments should be made to the roll-out and operation / commercialization of the data space (leaving the test-bed environment).

6.2.3. Operation phase for data space business models

In the operation phase of data space business models, the data space is rolled-out. As a consequence, the actual performance of the data space business models (in terms of users active, revenues generated, operational costs incurred) can be monitored. This is relevant input for evaluating whether the data space business model continues to produce a viable business model scenario for all stakeholders involved. In case an inviable scenario is obtained, stakeholders should collectively determine how this can be addressed through business model (re)design. For example, the revenue model of the business model may be altered or different forms of governance structures can potentially be selected. The goal is to ensure that data space operations can be maintained.

In addition to monitoring business model performance, stakeholders should also investigate what opportunities for scaling the data space can be considered to increase the viability and impact of the data space. Part of this activity involves defining what scaling strategy is pursued: for example, stakeholders may determine that the value proposition to service providers can be extended through providing support for different domains or through increasing the depth by which data exchange is facilitated. This can warrant different revenue models or help in achieving a larger user base. Depending on what scaling strategy is selected, the scaling intentions may have implications for the technical feasibility and viability of the data space business model (which should be assessed). For example, scaling the solution may demand from stakeholders to increase their database capacity or to scale internal operations. It should be assessed to what extent data space stakeholders involved are able to do so, or whether different stakeholders may have to be involved to facilitate this (which has implications for the data space business model design). For example, additional database service providers can be involved

for the business model design to support the increased need for database capacity. However, this logically has implications for how much value can be captured by other stakeholders. Once a viable business model design to support the selected scaling strategies is obtained, data space development can be scaled.

6.2.4. Scaling phase for data space business models

In the scaling phase for data space business models, the opportunities to further scale the data space (and thus the associated business model) are continuously assessed. Depending on the performance of the scaled business model, stakeholders should decide on whether the data space can be scaled further (and whether this makes sense from a viability and feasibility perspective) and what strategies can be considered to do so. Similar to the operation phase, data space stakeholders should therefore decide on the appropriate scaling strategy(ies) to consider and to evaluate whether a viable and feasible business scenario can be obtained for stakeholders involved. If needed, changes to the data space business model design may be needed to facilitate this.

6.3. Data space governance structure

A detailed view of how the data space governance structure fits for the data space development process is illustrated in Figure 37. In the following, we elaborate for each phase what activities should be undertaken and how these activities can be supported.

6.3.1. Exploration phase for data space governance structure

The exploration phase for the data space governance structure focuses on understanding what collaboration forms should be selected to support the deployment of the data space. This means that data space stakeholders should jointly explore and assess what organisational governance modes are most suitable given the characteristics of the stakeholders involved as well as the context in which the data space is positioned. This also means that stakeholders should define how responsibilities in terms of governance are distributed. Is a joint venture structure selected to accommodate this or are responsibilities shared amongst stakeholders involved? It calls for an understanding of what types of stakeholders are involved, whether these stakeholders have collaborated before and to what extent trust already exists between (part of the) stakeholders present at the table. This can influence what collaboration form (and consequently what governance mechanisms should be defined, see Section Governance models should be initially selected to support the deployment of the data space. Note that the distribution of responsibilities and decision making rights can be preliminary in nature and is to be tested as part of the piloting phase – changes can therefore occur (illustrating the

iterative nature of exploration and piloting): however, the distribution and sharing of decision making rights provide input towards the definition of the technical architecture needed to accommodate the deployment of the data space for piloting. Moreover, these decisions also provides input for data space business model design decisions. Accordingly, it is key that decision making on the governance structure takes place in the exploration phase such that the other aspects of data space development (technical architecture, business models) can already take this into account.

In addition to the organisational governance structure of the data space, stakeholders should also define how data governance is structured before the piloting phase can commence. Logically, the data governance structure is influenced by the type of data to share as part of the data space, which in turn is dependent on the context in which the data space is to be positioned (i.e. what type of initiative is pursued and what type of data should be shared, related to *data scope* in Figure 15). Consequently, stakeholders should define the initial procedures, policies and standards for data sharing: if the organisations engage in data exchange, what procedures should be followed to do so? How can we preserve the quality of the data that is exchanged by means of standards to be defined? How can we ensure that accessibility, but also privacy of data is enabled through policies to be installed? What contractual agreements should be defined between data space users (data owners, service providers, data users) to facilitate this? The objective for the exploration phase is to ensure that an initial data governance structure is in place to facilitate data exchange between data space users as part of the piloting phase. Again, design decisions made are subject to change and can be improved upon as part of the piloting phase.

Figure 37: Data space governance structure to support data space development

6.3.2. Piloting phase for data space governance structure

In the piloting phase for data space governance structure, the design decisions regarding the organisational and data governance structure should be evaluated: through trialling of the data space as part of pilots or projects, insights should be derived on the *appropriateness or suitability* of the design decisions made, and whether design decisions should be changed to support the deployment and roll-out of the data space. Completion of this phase should result in agreed upon, validated designs regarding the governance structures in place such that the data space can be rolled-out in practice. For one, does the organisational governance mode selected create *trust* between stakeholders to continue to collaborate as part of the data space? Does it support and motivate users of the data space to share and exchange data as part of the data space? Note that this builds upon the insights generated through the evaluation of the data space and application specific business models – if the organisational governance hinders value co-creation and capture (for example, the organisational governance is too restricted for service providers to join the data space or does not lead to acceptable returns in terms of value capture for stakeholders involved), the governance mechanisms or collaboration forms in place should be altered.

A similar case can be made for the selected data governance mechanisms: it should be evaluated by means of pilot testing whether the data governance mechanisms selected enable data space users to provide new value propositions as part of the application-specific business models. For example, the data governance mechanisms in place may pose restrictions on what data can be shared between service providers or other data space users or may cause data to not be accessible. As a result, potential value creation may be inhibited which can make the application-business models enabled by the data space inviable or undesirable. Data space stakeholders should therefore evaluate what the impact is of the data governance mechanisms in place and whether these mechanisms can lead to viable data space and application-specific business models. Ultimately, the organisational and data governance structure selected should help the data space achieve its business objectives and should motivate the roll-out and exploitation of the data space in practice.

As a check to verify whether the governance structure for the data space is complete (and thus warrants moving towards the next phase), the high level governance requirements for data spaces as presented in Appendix C can be used. These requirements have been defined in D2.1 (Cornelisse, 2022) and are linked to the templates proposed by SITRA for governance decision making (Pitkänen & Luoma-Kyyny, 2022). Accordingly, if certain requirements are not met, stakeholders can refer to the templates needed to concretize these aspects of data space governance further.

6.3.3. Operation phase for data space governance structure

In the operation phase for the data space governance structure, the appropriateness of the selected governance mechanisms and collaboration forms should be monitored. In contrast to the piloting phase (test-bed settings such as pilots in projects or controlled environments), the operation phase represents real-world deployment which may highlight issues or concerns regarding governance that were previously unaddressed. Such issues should be resolved to support the (continued) exploitation of the data space, ensuring that the business objectives for the data space can be satisfied. In addition, the operation phase may also involve the exploration of scaling intentions (expanding on the current user base, diversifying the type of users to consider or connecting to related data space initiatives). These scaling intentions can influence the appropriateness of the design decisions made regarding organisational and data governance. For example, if a data space initiative expands from facilitating data sharing between manufacturing companies to also include organisations from other domains (such as logistics), changes to the data governance and organisational governance mechanisms may be required (i.e. who is allowed to join the data space?; do we need to share additional types of data and if so, how will we manage, store and share this data?). In close connection to evaluating what new application-specific business models can be enabled (and whether this is worthwhile), stakeholders should assess what the impact is of data governance mechanisms on existing as well as new business models enabled by the data space. This should provide insights on whether it makes sense to pursue scaling intentions or whether the current status quo for the data space should be followed. Note that changing current data or organisational governance mechanisms is impactful: it can represent different ways of operation or collaboration which can be met with resistance. Therefore, stakeholders should also understand what the implications of changing the data or organisational governance structure may be (and how this contrasts to the additional value propositions that can be enabled by doing so). Again, the high level governance requirements (see Appendix C) may be used to support the understanding of whether the governance structure is complete

6.3.4. Scaling phase for data space governance structure

As part of the scaling phase, the data space governance structure should continuously be evaluated as different scaling intentions are pursued. Analogously to the analysis conducted for the operation phase, the appropriateness of the organisational and data governance mechanisms should be evaluated in light of whether both existing and new business models can adequately be supported.

7. Conclusions

In this deliverable, we have presented an approach to support the design of governance and business models in the context of data space development. This approach constitutes a conceptual background of three interlinked perspectives on data space development (namely, the development of *data space business models*, *application-specific business models* and *data space governance structure*) for which designs are needed. Each of these perspectives is concretized by means of a dedicated design process as part of the approach; accordingly, for each perspective a concrete process can be followed to guide the design.

Review of existing literature has highlighted the need for such an approach: although the technical architecture of data spaces (in terms of components, roles to consider) has received significant attention, less emphasis has been placed on the business and governance aspects of data space development. It is however essential to consider what business models can be enabled by means of a new data space to motivate its existence. Additionally, interactions and collaborations call for governance on organizations and data exchange to enable value propositions as part of new business models.

The contributions of this deliverable are as follows:

- It stresses the need for three perspectives on data space development for which design decisions should be made: *data space business models* (what is in it for those that provide the data space?), *application-specific business models* (what is in it for those that use the data space?) and *data space governance structure* (how do we coordinate interactions and collaborations to enable value creation?).
- It provides a structured comprehensive approach including tool guidance per perspective to operationalize the approach in practice. These tools are based on insights from literature and offer a step by step discussion on what design decisions to make in terms of business models or governance modes for data spaces.
- The approach proposed as part of the H2020 Ploutos project can be used to fully support the design of application-specific business models for data spaces. Given the often standardized roles and interactions involved for data spaces, an altered version of this approach can be used for data space business models. Here, the reference model proposed can serve as a valuable starting point.
- Although tools have been identified to support data space governance design decisions (DSC use case definition and SITRA templates for governance definition), there is a lack of an integrated approach to support design decisions for data space governance. The approach proposed as part of this deliverable (based on a synthesis of governance literature and tooling) serves

as a fruitful starting point, which can be refined and detailed over time to aid the decision making.

The full approach will be used by the SILLs in ZeroW to support the development of data spaces for each of the SILLs, clarifying what business decisions (in terms of business models and governance structure) should be made and when these should be made, as well as how the local ecosystems and data spaces can be scaled over time. Through this hands-on application, we intend to collect feedback to further improve on the approach, better understanding the usability of the approach but also its strengths and weaknesses. As indicated in Chapter 5.4.1.1, we already see that aspects of governance decision making can be further detailed and refined to offer additional handholds to users. As part of future work (specifically D2.6 and D2.7), we intend to provide such support. Additionally, future work will also focus on the development of *data space archetypes* to further help design decision making on data space development (included as part of improvements for the approach for T2.4).

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Appendix A

Example business models developed through Ploutos collaborative business modelling approach

This business model design addresses a food sharing platform being offered. One can see that a platform provider acts as orchestrator of the model (in purple), offering integration and matching between food producers and charities in need of (food) support. Through this matching, FLW can be reduced. To support the transportation of food, volunteers are included / involved as the platform to help charities in transportation activities and the collection and distribution of goods. The sharing platform includes protocols and policies on who can access the platform (food producers as well as charities should be legally registered) and who can share or access data (food producers can indicate what charities to consider). This stresses the importance of data and organizational governance to support business model activities.

This business model design supports the roll-out of carbon farming services to farmers. This service is offered by a service provider that collects data on farming practices at the farmer and provides advice on how farmers can improve. Through their efforts, farmer can earn carbon credits in the process. In this business model, a collaboration form is selected in which farmers sell these carbon credits to the (biological) wholesaler (who needs these credits to strive for CO₂ neutrality) at a premium price. If these farmers already collaborate with the respective wholesaler, the relationship between farmers and the wholesaler is expected to improve. To support the service, data collection and exchange is needed with parties such as technology providers (to collect and transform data into insights), certification providers (to establish trust in carbon farming processes) and data analysts (to provide advice to farmers on how to improve). Logically, agreements have to be made here on how this data exchange is governed between parties and how this can be re-used.

Appendix B

Example of templates produced as part of use case definition (source (Data Sharing Coalition, 2021))

Use case playbook / Appendix / Examples on Context description template

Context description template example: Sharing freight transport data with insurers

<p>How to use this template</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Start by describing the current situation and how this results in a opportunity or challenge for your organisation 2. Describe how data sharing can address the opportunity or challenge. Keep the use case description short and focus on the impact of the use case 3. Look in the appendix for examples of completed templates for DSC use cases 	<p>Use case name: <i>Sharing freight transport data with insurers</i></p>
	<p>Describe the current situation:</p> <p><i>Logistics parties insure their goods when they move within and across borders. Currently, information regarding the status of the goods for Insurers is available via paper-based trade documentation with unstructured data. This leads to a lack of insight for the Insurer on the status of the goods and potential risks involved with the goods, resulting in higher insurance costs for logistics parties when insuring their goods</i></p>
	<p>Describe the opportunity or challenge:</p> <p><i>Open up electronic trade documentation (e-CMR) to Insurers in a structured and controlled way for them to develop operational efficiencies, new products and new data-driven services (e.g. faster reconciliation of shipment data for claim handling process)</i></p>
	<p>Which of these categories matches your opportunity or challenge:</p> <p> <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Automation of certain (repetitive) tasks <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Difficulty in assessing certain risks due to a lack of information <input type="checkbox"/> Other: ... <input type="checkbox"/> New insights enabling new value propositions <input type="checkbox"/> Inefficiency in a value chain </p>
<p>Describe how data sharing can address the above situation:</p> <p><i>e-CMR data is shared by e-CMR providers on behalf of the Carrier with Insurers. The e-CMR data is shared in a structured and machine readable way, allowing the Insurers to make the claim handling process more efficient</i></p>	

Template filled in for data sharing use case in the context of freight transport insurance. Questions posed help in identifying the value of the use case, what is being solved and how the data sharing use case enables problem solving.

Description template example: Sharing freight transport data with insurers

<p>How to use this template</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Start by filling in the blocks. Limit your use case description to the components needed to show the value of the use case 2. Fill in the actors per role and the value per role 3. Use the Interaction template to map all relevant actors and interactions 4. Find completed templates as examples in the appendix 	<p>Use case name: <i>Sharing freight transport data with insurers</i></p>
	<p>Describe the use case:</p> <p><i>Structured and machine-readable electronic trade documentation (e-CMR) is made available by logistics organisations for the Insurer that covers their cargo whilst keeping the data under control of the Entitled party. Incorporating structured data from the shipment during claim handling enables a more efficient claim handling process</i></p>
	<p>Initial scale of use case:</p> <p> <input type="checkbox"/> Proof of Concept <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Pilot <input type="checkbox"/> Production <input type="checkbox"/> Other:... </p>
	<p>Describe the data shared:</p> <p><i>Structured and machine-readable freight transport data in e-CMR format, which is an electronic version of the consignment note (paper version is called CMR)</i></p>
<p>What analysis is done on the data:</p> <p><i>The analysis needed for the claim handling process in a more efficient and fault tolerant way due to the structured and machine-readable e-CMR data</i></p>	
<p>Introducing data services and roles</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. <i>Data service:</i> Any service offered by a data service provider aimed at exchanging or processing data 2. <i>Data service consumer:</i> Actor uses the data service offered by the data service provider 3. <i>Data service provider:</i> Actor that offers a data service to the data service consumer 4. <i>Entitled Party:</i> Entity which has rights over data, which may include storage of data as well as access and usage of data 5. <i>Enabling party</i> provides services or tools that enable data sharing 	<p>Data service consumer(s):</p> <p>Who fulfils this role: <i>Insurer</i></p> <p>Value for Data service consumer(s): <i>Increase efficiency; less administrative burden due to structured data</i></p>
	<p>Data service provider(s):</p> <p>Who fulfils this role: <i>e-CMR provider</i></p> <p>Value for Data service provider(s): <i>Increase revenue from fee per data transaction</i></p>
	<p>Interaction model:</p> <p>Use the Interaction template to map all relevant actors and interactions</p>
	<p>Entitled party:</p> <p>Who fulfils this role: <i>Carrier (Claim issuer)</i></p> <p>Value for Entitled party: <i>Improve speed of claim handling process and lower cost</i></p>
<p>Enabling party/ies:</p> <p>Who fulfils this role: <i>iSHARE</i></p> <p>Value for Enabling party/ies: <i>Enable new application of iSHARE scheme</i></p>	

Subsequent template refines what roles are involved, who should be mapped to these roles and in what context the data sharing use case is considered.

Potential template example: Sharing freight transport data with insurers

How to use this template

- Describe the potential value for the Entitled party first, as without sufficient potential value the Entitled party will not participate in the use case
- Complete the table for the other roles with a score as shown in the legend
- Score the potential of this use case on societal impact
- Conclude on the potential value by adding up the scores per role. As a rule of thumb, every role in the use case should have at least 2 points (excluding societal impact)
- Complete the template for the actors separately if you have very different actors per role
- Look in the appendix for examples of this template
- Interview stakeholders to validate the result of the template if necessary

Note: The goal of this template is to consider potential value from perspective of different roles. The scores only offer an indication, as they are subjective

Use case name: *Sharing freight transport data with insurers*

What is the potential value for the Entitled party? *Faster claim handling process
Lower cost*

For the Entitled party, does the potential value outweigh the perceived risk associated with sharing data? **Yes / No**

Questions to answer to assess potential value for Data service provider(s), Data service consumer(s) and Enabling party/ies

		Data service provider(s)	Data service consumer(s)	Enabling party/ies
Potential revenue increase	Is there potential for extra revenue from new or improved products or services?	-	-	-
	Is there potential for extra revenue from improved customer relation?	1	-	-
	Is there potential for extra revenue from transaction fees from revealing data?	2	-	-
	Is there potential for extra revenue from other sources?	-	-	2
Potential cost reduction	Is there potential for cost reduction due to improved internal efficiency?	-	2	-
	Is there potential for cost reduction due to improved risk management?	-	2	-
	Is there potential for cost reduction from other sources?	-	-	-
Other	Contribution to strategic objectives, part of obligations or ethical branding	-	-	-
	Total per role	3	4	2
Potential societal impact	What is the potential societal impact? This includes many topics, examples are improving sustainability, improving health, reducing poverty, increasing equality or contributing to a more circular economy			-

Examples in appendix

Legend:
High = 2
Low = 1
None = -

For each of the roles included, indicative value creation potential is indicated. On the basis of this, the motivation for pursuing the data sharing use case is strengthened (in case significant value can be captured).

Interaction complexity template example: Sharing freight transport data with insurers

How to use this template

- Start with the results from the Use case scoping step in mind
- Mark the level of interaction complexity for all 5 questions in the table
- Take the average the 5 answers to get the final score of the assessment
- Use this score to estimate what facilities are needed to establish trust and interoperability. A high score means that more extensive facilities are needed to arrange the necessary trust and interoperability in the use case
- Look in the appendix for examples of completed templates
- Interview stakeholders to validate the result of the template if necessary

Note: The goal of this template is to consider interaction complexity from different perspectives. The scores only offer an indication, as they are very subjective

Use case name: *Sharing freight transport data with insurers*

Per question select the answer corresponding to the use case situation

The two factors	Questions per driver	Per question select the answer corresponding to the use case situation		
		Low interaction complexity	Medium interaction complexity	High interaction complexity
Actor complexity	What is the number of actors involved in the use case?	Few actors		Many actors
	What degree of competition is there between the parties involved that is relevant for this use case?	No competition		Major competition
	If different actors fulfil the same role, how different are these actors?	Very similar / Not applicable		Very different
Data complexity	How different are the types of data shared in your use case?	One type		Many types
	How sensitive is the data being shared for your use case?	Not sensitive		Highly sensitive

Examples in appendix

Lastly, the degree of actor (organizational governance) and data (data governance) complexity is assessed, providing clear input to what design decisions for these aspects should be made.

Appendix C

High level governance requirements for data space development in connection to D2.1 (Cornelisse, 2022)

The following table is an overview of high level governance requirements for a OFLW dataspace from D2.1 (Cornelisse, 2022) including the mapping onto the Rulebook templates/checklists developed by SITRA (Pitkänen & Luoma-Kyyny, 2022). The left side of the table represents the requirements that have emerged through D2.1. These have been linked to the templates (right side) proposed by SITRA, such that it becomes apparent what templates provide answers towards satisfying the requirements for high level governance definition. Each of the templates used includes the 'codes' proposed by SITRA (for example TS.3.2 or B0.4.2) for easy traceability.

ID	Comment	Rulebook template / checklist
IM	Identity management	
IM-G01	Admission	TS.3.2 Access control and Identities
IM-G02	Storing participant data	B0.4.2 Data governance
IM-G03	Authentication	TS.3.2 Access control and Identities
IM-G04	Participant metadata	B0.4.2 Data governance, B0.5.2 Data usage control, TS.2.2 Metadata and data formats
IM-G05	Leaving	TS.6.2 Personal data management solution
IM-G06	Clean-up	B0.4.2 Data governance, TS.6.2 Personal data management solution
IM-G07	Operational evaluation	TS.3.3 Data usage control solution
IM-G08	Evaluation of identity providers	TS.3.3 Data usage control solution
TE	Trusted exchange	
TE-G01	Certification request	B0.5.1 Data ecosystem services
TE-G02	Certification meta information	B0.4.2 Data governance, B0.5.1 Data ecosystem services
TE-G03	Certification response	B0.5.1 Data ecosystem services
AU	Access & Usage control/policies	
AU-G01	Revoke usage	B0.5.2 Data usage control; TS.3.2 Access control and Identities, TS.3.3 Data usage control solution
MD	Metadata & Discovery services	

MD-G01	Semantic model for discovery	B0.4.2 Data governance, TS.2.2 Metadata and data formats
MD-G02	Revoking descriptions	B0.5.2 Data usage control, TS.3.3 Data usage control solution
BU	Business Agreements	
BU-G01	Business model intermediary services	B0.3.1 Business case
BU-G02	Intellectual Property Rights	B0.4.2 Data governance
BU-G03	Domain Data standards	B0.4.2 Data governance, TS.2.2 Metadata and data formats
BU-G04	Scaling strategy	B0.3.1 Business case, B0.4.2 Data governance

ID	Comment	Rulebook template / checklist
OP	Operational Agreements	
OP-G01	Operational model for intermediary services	B0.5.1 Data ecosystem services, B0.5.3 Consent management,
OP-G02	Operational Service Level agreements	B0.5.1 Data ecosystem services, B0.5.6 Operational monitoring and administration
OP-G03	Operational model for supporting services	B0.5.1 Data ecosystem services, B0.5.3 Consent management
OP-G04	Accounting scheme	B0.3.3 Data network solution fundamentals, B0.5.1 Data ecosystem services,
OP-G05	Billing/charging scheme	B0.3.3 Data network solution fundamentals, B0.5.1 Data ecosystem services
OP-G06	Smart contracts	B0.5.1 Data ecosystem services
OP-G07	Value of data	B0.3.2 Data value, B0.4.2 Data governance
OR	Organisational Agreements	
OR-G01	Organisation	B0.2.2 Stakeholder roles, B0.2.3 Stakeholder rights and responsibilities
OR-G02	Identities	B0.5.3 Consent management, TS.3.2 Access control and Identities
OR-G03	Authorisation	TS.3.2 Access control and Identities
OR-G04	Intermediary services	B0.2.2 Stakeholder roles, B0.2.3 Stakeholder rights and responsibilities
OR-G05	Overarching cooperation agreements	B0.5.3 Consent management, TS.6.2 Personal data management solution
OR-G06	Continuity model	TS.4.1 Change control
OR-G07	Laws, administrative rules or regulations	B0.5.2 Data usage control
FD	Federation of services	<i>Not specifically covered but part of:</i>
FD-G01	Cross dataspace compliancy	B0.4.2 Data governance; B0.5.2 Data usage control

FD-G02	Focussing on access, usage and finance	B0.4.2 Data governance; B0.5.2 Data usage control
FD-G03	Dealing with data life-cycle and ending the collaboration	B0.4.2 Data governance; B0.5.2 Data usage control